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D3.4 Reports on learning activities for GEPI Committees – v2

Project Acronym: ATHENA

Title: Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

Grant Agreement n°: 101006416

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

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Version history

Version	Date	Comments / Changes	Author/ Reviewer
0.1	27.01.23	Draft version sent to the project consortium and the Steering Committee for review	Sara Amador, Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Perello and Marlene Santacruz
1.0	31.01.23	Final version to be submitted after inclusion of comments from the project consortium and the Steering Committee	Project consortium and Steering Committee

Document Information

Project Acronym	ATHENA
Project Title	Implementing gender equality plans to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe
Project Number	101006416
Instrument	CSA - Coordination and support action
Topic	SwafS-09-2018-2019-2020 - Supporting research organisations to implement gender equality plans
Project Start Date	01/02/2021
Project Duration	48 months
Work Package	WP3
Task	T3.3
Deliverable	D3.4 Reports on learning activities for GEPI Committees – v2
Due Date	31/01/2023
Submission Date	31/01/2023
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Deliverable Responsible	PP1 – Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation (CE)
Version	1.0
Status	Final
Author(s)	Sara Amador, Beatrice Avagnina, Michelle Perello and Marlene Santacruz
Reviewers	Steering Committee

¹ PU= Public, CO=Confidential, only for members of the Consortium (including the Commission Services), CL=Classified, as referred in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

ACIISI	Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la Información
CE	Consulta Europa Projects and Innovation S.L.
D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
FRCT	Fundo Regional da Ciência e Tecnologia (FRCT)
GE	Gender equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
GEPI Committees	Gender Equality Plans Implementation Committees
GA	Grant Agreement
JSI	Jozef Stefan Institute
RFO	Research funding organization
RPO	Research performing organization
T	Task
UB	University of Bucharest
UJK	Jan Kochanowski University in Kielce
ULPGC	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
URAK	University of Ruse Angel Kanchev
UVSK SAV	Ustav Vyskumu Socialnej Komunikacie Slovenskej
WP	Work package

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose and scope

The present deliverable, entitled 'Reports on the learning activities for the GEPI Committees' presents the reports on the capacity building activities towards gender equality developed under the ATHENA framework. These activities, undertaken under project work package (WP) 3 'Capacity building activities', are targeted to the whole institutional community of the project partners institutions, i.e. Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) and Research Funding Organizations (RFOs). Thus, target groups involve researchers, professors, high and middle management, administrative staff, human resources staff as well as students for the case of RPOs.

A training programme was designed and implemented to empower the project Gender Equality Plans Implementation (GEPI) Committees towards institutional change in terms of gender aspects. Additionally, the present document reports on the 2nd project Mutual Learning Workshop (MLW) that was carried out on 17 January 2023. This MLW was aimed at sharing and commonly learn from the experiences of each ATHENA partner in the process of implementing their tailored Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and the organisation of trainings and events. Project partners also discussed the key aspects to be considered for the next phases of GEPs implementation and monitoring.

1.2 Document structure

This deliverable describes:

- The objectives and schedule of the ATHENA Gender Training Programme organised under the ATHENA framework (**section 2**).
- The specific trainings carried out by each ATHENA implementing their GEP, including the training outlines and the event report (**section 3**).
- The 2nd Mutual Learning Workshop and its results (**section 4**).

2. The Gender Training Programme

Training is one of the mandatory requirements set by the Horizon Europe eligibility criterion². This criterion requires that the GEPs include awareness-raising and training actions on gender equality and unconscious bias for staff and decision-making positions. In fact, the ATHENA consortium consider that training actions are key to increase sensitivity to gender equality at the same time as giving people the skills and knowledge to be engaged towards it.

² The Gender Equality Plan (GEP) eligibility criterion of the Horizon Europe Framework for Research and Innovation 2021-2027. Find more information at <https://op.europa.eu/es/publication-detail/-/publication/ffcb06c3-200a-11ec-bd8e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-232129669>

ATHENA RPOs and RFOs implementing GEPs have designed and put in place a gender training programme under T3.2. This training programme addressed the ATHENA GEPI (Gender Equality Plan Implementation) Committees. It was a ‘train the trainers’ activity, aimed at qualifying the GEPI Committees for them to be able to promote the institutional transformation in terms of gender aspects. As a continuity, the T3.3 foresees the development and implementation of a gender training programme devoted to the whole institutional community. This document presents the outline and event report of each one of these institutional training programmes.

2.1 Objective of the training programme

The aim of the capacity building is to **create and increase sensitivity of the whole project partner institution to gender equality at the same time as providing with the knowledge and skills to be engaged towards the institutional transformation.**

2.2 Structure of the training programme

Each ATHENA RPO/RFO implementing their GEPs designed a gender training programme under project task T3.3, which is deployed to the whole institutional community, i.e, the internal staff (researchers, professors, administrative staff, human resources (HR) staff) and, for the case of the RPOs, students.

The training programme is composed of at least 5 modules, which focus on different topics and address different groups in accordance with each institution’s needs. Each ATHENA institution has developed the topics and modules of the training programme tailored to the results of the gender diagnostic carried out under WP2. As for the modality, they are delivered both face-to-face and online. The project target is to train at least 150 participants at each project institution.

Table 1 summarises the abovementioned and additional main characteristics of the gender training programme.

Table 1. Structure and main characteristics of the gender training programme

Target group	The whole institution, i.e., institutional staff (and students for the case of RPOs). The training programme should engage the whole organisation, its different levels and roles (The ATHENA target groups (High management; HR professionals; administrative staff; researchers).
Indicator	At least 150 people trained in each ATHENA institution.
Topic	ATHENA institutions determine the specific topics of the programme and its modules based on the results of the assessment carried out under WP2 .
Objective	Specified by each ATHENA institution. The training programme should at least: - Cover awareness raising of the whole institution towards gender equality. - Address unconscious bias for staff and decision makers. (These requirements are set in line with the mandatory process-related requirements set by the EC).

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Modality	Face-to-face or online.
Format	The training programme may be delivered in different ways, for instance traditional lecture sessions, courses of study or webinars.
Developed by	ATHENA consortium/ ATHENA GEPI Committee members/ Gender experts
Delivered by	ATHENA consortium/ ATHENA GEPI Committee members/ Gender experts
Training programme implementation	From M14 (March 2022) to M22 (November 2022) . The training programme is implemented on an ongoing basis.
Duration of each module	Indicative duration: 2 hours minimum and 10 hours maximum for each module (thus, the total duration of a 5-module training programme is around 10 hours minimum and 50 hours maximum).
Language	English or national languages , based on each ATHENA RPOs/RFOs needs.

Project partners were also encouraged to cover other needed different topics. A non-exhaustive list of potential topics and objective for the gender training programme were identified and shared with partners, as detailed in *D3.2 Programme and material of the Gender Training Programme*. Project partners were provided with guidance to develop and implement their gender training programmes, as well with templates for training proposal outline and modules report.

There were various cases where project partners repeated a module or delivered an extra one, following participant's requests or as a result of identifying further opportunities to emphasise specific topics. A total of **37 trainings** were delivered between May 2022- January 2023. The trainings involved a total of **1231 participants**.

3. ATHENA Gender Training Programmes

The Table 2 reports the final topics of each ATHENA training programme as well as each of its specific modules. As it can be seen, all the ATHENA institutions that implement GEPs have planned their gender training programmes under T3.3. The Agency for Research, Innovation and Information Society from the regional government of the Canary islands (ACIISI – GOBCAN), organised the training addressed to the whole institutional staff in December 2021. This organisation employs a considerably smaller number of employees (around 26 workers) compared to the rest of the project research institutions. Thus, it organised a training programme in which both the GEPI Committee members and the institutional staff participated. Event report of this training may be consulted within project deliverable '*D3.3 – Report on learning activities for GEPI Committees – v1*'. Similarly, FRCT also employs a considerably smaller number of employees. Nonetheless, despite the institution's reduced number of employees and significant workload, efforts were made to ensure that at least fifty per cent of the institution participated in each of these trainings.

Table 2. Topics and modules of each ATHENA training programme

ATHENA institution	Training topic	Module 1	Module 2	Module 3	Module 4	Module 5	Module 6
JSI	Gender equality at JSI	Unconscious bias	Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making	Work-life balance	Ethics and integrity in research	Gender equality in career progression and recruitment	n/a
UJK	Equal opportunities in science and research	Unconscious bias in the workplace	The gender dimension in research - including gender issues in research	Equal opportunities and non-discrimination in research projects - universal project framework design	Equality in career progression and recruitment	Inclusive language	n/a
UB	A Gender Equal University: Beyond Stereotypes and Biases	A Gender Equal University: Beyond Stereotypes and Biases in the University Administration	A Gender Equal University: Teaching beyond stereotypes and biases	A Gender Equal University: useful concepts for students	Preventing Gender Based Violence: recognize it and act.	Mainstreaming Gender in Inter-disciplinary Academic Research	n/a
URAK	Sustainable equality of women and men in the science	Unconscious bias and gender-based violence	Work-life balance and organizational culture.	Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making	Gender equality in career progression and recruitment.	Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content.	n/a
ULPGC	Advancing towards gender equality at the ULPGC	Leadership and career progression in the company	Leadership and career progression in public administration	Leadership and career progression in research	Prevention and action against gender-based violence	Methodologies applied to gender studies in the humanities and social sciences	Human rights and gender equality
UVSK SAV	Gender equality in science	Introduction to Gender Equality	Gender in research	Gender sensitive management	Empowerment	Sexual harassment on workplace	Gender sensitive language
FRCT	Gender equality at FRCT	Unconscious bias	The gender dimension in research	Work-life balance and organisational culture	How to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment	Tools for an inclusive language	n/a

The Table 3 below shows the training programme timeline. As it can be seen, most of the modules were delivered between October-November 2022. The training programme was expected to be finished by the end of November 2022. However, due to some administrative issues and institutional availability, there were some events that had to be postponed to December 2022/January 2023.

Table 3. Timeline of the ATHENA training programmes

ATHENA institution	Module 1	Module 2	Module 3	Module 4	Module 5	Module 6
JSI	5 October 2022	13 October 2022	25 October 2022	27 October 2022	11 November 2022	n/a
UJK	27 October 2022	7 November 2022	9 November 2022	22 November 2022	29 November 2022	n/a
UB	9 June 2022 and 20 October 2022	26 October 2022	25 & 29 Nov 2022	16 November 2022	27 January 2023	n/a
ULPGC	11 November 2022	11 November 2022	11 November 2022	3 November 2022	24-26 May & 1 June 2022	12 Dec 2022
UVSK SAV	13 May 2022	23 May 2022 and 14 October 2022	26 October 2022	21 September 2022	18 March and 19 September 2022	28 April 2022
URAK	28 October 2022	25 October 2022	14 November 2022	22 November 2022	29 November 2022	n/a
FRCT	19 September 2022	20 October 2022	3 October 2022	10 October 2022	17 October 2022	n/a

Next subsections present the event report for every module of the Gender Training Programme organised by the ATHENA institutions implementing their GEP.

3.1 JSI Gender Training Programme:

Training Topic: *Gender equality at JSI*

Module 1: Unconscious bias and its effects in the work environment

General information

Venue	JSI and Zoom
Date	5. 10. 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Prof. Dr Milica Antić Gaber,
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana
Total number of participants	62
Number of high and middle managers participants	6
Number of HR professionals participants*	NA
Number of professors and researchers participants	49
Number of administrative professionals participants	7
Number of students participants	NA
Total duration of the module (hours)	2
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Hybrid format (lecture room/Zoom)

*: JSI does not have an HR professional nor a dedicated HR unit

Agenda

10.00 - 10.05 Welcome address, Prof. Dr. Boštjan Zalar, Director of JSI

10.05 - 10.15 Gender equality at the Jožef Stefan Institute, Dr. Romana Jordan, JSI

10.15 - 11.00 Unconscious bias in the research and academic environment, Prof. Dr. Milica Antić Gaber, Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana

11.00 - 11.10 Questions and discussion

11.10 - 11.20 Coffee break

11.20 - 12.00 Workshop: Raising awareness of unconscious bias, moderated by Alma Mehle, JSI

Event pictures

Photo: Marjan Verč

Methodology and content

Content of the module

In this training, Prof. Dr Milica Antić Gaber introduced gender equality and unconscious bias to JSI staff. Using practical examples from academia and research, we learned what unconscious bias is, how we recognise it and how it can affect our judgement and decision-making in a professional environment.

In the second part of the training, we used practical activities to raise awareness of unconscious bias and discussed practical examples and possible solutions to reduce its negative impact in the work environment.

Methodology

The training was held in a hybrid format, live in the JSI's main lecture room and online via Zoom.

The first part of the training was a lecture, followed by a group discussion. The second part was a workshop, which included practical exercises with poll-taking, followed by comments on the results and group discussion. Additional practical examples were given to promote group discussion.

Tools and techniques

Tools and techniques used in the lecture: PowerPoint presentation, data from JSI's survey, case studies, photos, and discussion.

Tools and techniques used in the workshop: PowerPoint presentation, practical exercise: IAT test, online poll taking, theoretical/practical examples, discussion.

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Participants' feedback

The feedback on the training was very positive. We've received several comments on the event being great, but several participants wished more heads of departments had attended, and it might make sense to think about how to do a wider outreach. Some felt that although the lecture was interesting, there were not enough suggestions on how to improve the situation in practice.

Some participants felt that such lectures should be compulsory, at least for all heads of departments, since some participants commented that they experience sexism at the workplace and feel this kind of training could be eye-opening. There were also comments from participants wanting to learn more about JSI's procedures for reporting sexism and mobbing.

We've also received comments regarding intersectionality and interest in learning more about this component in regard to gender equality: gender equality and LGBTQ+, nationality etc.

I wonder what women's real aspirations are to fill these positions more equally. Also, there has been more and more talk recently about a more equal distribution of maternity leave - how many women (and men) actually want that? What are the concerns?

Successes and difficulties

Main success and difficulties related to this specific module

The module was, overall, very well received. It was the first module on gender equality training, and we were pleased to see that it was discussed at JSI the following week. More than half of our participants joined via Zoom, which confirms that the hybrid format was the right choice; however, it was more difficult to conduct the workshop with practical exercises in a hybrid format. Another difficulty was staying within the given time frame due to prolonged lectures and discussions, which resulted in participants leaving before the workshop in the second part was concluded.

Improvement suggestions for the future modules

Shorter, more focused lectures, with more time for open discussion, would maximize the effect of the training. More focus on opening group discussions with relevant questions. Chosen exercises should be simple for the live and online audience to actively participate.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

JSI's sub-page for Gender Equality: <https://www.ijs.si/ijsw/EnakostSpolov> .

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Module 2: Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making

General information

Venue	Jožef Stefan Institute, main lecture hall
Date	October 13, 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Mirjana Dimc Perko, MBA Prof. Miha Čekada
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Incon – Investment and Management Consulting d.o.o. Jožef Stefan Institute
Total number of participants	83
Number of high and middle managers participants	9
Number of HR professionals participants	NA
Number of professors and researchers participants	64
Number of administrative professionals participants	10
Number of students participants	NA
Total duration of the module (hours)	2 hours

Agenda

10:00-10:05 Prof. Dr Barbara Malič, Gender Equality at Jožef Stefan Institute (introduction)

10:05-10:45 Mirjana Dimc Perko, MBA, director of Incon – Investment and Management Consulting d.o.o., Gender balance in leadership and management (lecture)

10:45-11:00 Prof. Dr Miha Čekada, Jožef Stefan Institute, Fraction of women in the management of Jožef Stefan Institute in the last 30 years (lecture)

11:00-11:10 Q&A

11:10-11:20 Break

11:20-12:10 Round-table discussion on gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making moderated by Prof. Barbara Malič

Participants:

- Prof. Dr Maja Ravnikar, director of the National Institute of Biology
- Sonja Šmuc, M.Sc., executive director of Blueberry company
- Dr Peter Venturini, executive director of HELIOS Resins company
- Prof. Dr Boštjan Zalar, director of Jožef Stefan Institute

Event pictures

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Photo: Marjan Verč

Methodology and content

The short introduction to the module given by Prof. Dr Barbara Malič included a short description of the state of gender equality at the institute before the kick-off of the Athena project and the activities that took place afterwards.

The focus of the lecture of Ms Mirjana Dimc Perko, MBA, was on gender balance in leadership and management. Numerous analyses of the performance of companies show that gender balance in leadership positions and management contributes to better results for the companies. Still, despite this fact, the progress in gender balance in management is very slow. In addition to gender balance, the lecturer addressed some general stereotypes and reasons why analysts believe that progress in gender equality in leadership positions is slow, the impact of the COVID period, and some interesting statistics that negate these stereotypes.

Prof. Dr Miha Čekada analysed the share of women in management positions at Jožef Stefan Institute in the period 1992 – 2022. The input data were obtained from public sources. In 1993 it was for the first time that a woman became the head of a research department; one year later, the first woman became a member of the Scientific Council of the institute. With time, the number of women in leadership positions increased but only until about 2015-2018, and then it regressed. The reasons are not clear and would require additional analysis. Furthermore, it was shown that, on average, the age of female heads of research departments progressively increases, which is not the case for male colleagues.

The interactive part of the module was a round-table discussion. Both female and male representatives of leadership positions from academic and non-academic sectors, i.e., directors of two research institutes and executive directors of two companies, were asked to present their views on gender equality in leadership positions and measures to improve gender balance in leading positions.

Methodology:

- theoretical (lecture of M.D.Perko),
- practical (lecture of M. Čekada),
- round-table discussion.

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Tools and techniques

Main tools and techniques included:

- Lectures: PowerPoint presentations,
- Round-table discussion, which included questions from the audience.

Participants' feedback

We've received positive feedback on the event. One quite frequent comment was that such events were needed. Again, several participants commented that more heads of departments should attend the training. One comment was that it was good that the director of our institute participated in the module and explained his views on the topic of gender equality in the round-table discussion.

Several participants expressed a wish that in future, we organize a discussion on topics of career development for female researchers and career progression for female researchers in connection with having children. Some participants would like to see a broader debate on how a female researcher should develop her career, given that it is difficult to go on postdoctoral training and conferences when having small children. Interestingly, the question of the motivation of JSI's female researchers to hold leadership positions was raised.

One participant commented that it would be interesting to learn more about the psychological aspect of gender relations, which is the foundation of the equality we strive to achieve.

Successes and difficulties

Main success and difficulties related to this specific module.

The topic of the module was interesting for the staff. The audience followed the lectures as well as the round-table discussion.

Having a break between the two parts was a good idea, as discussions could continue in a less formal environment. However, the break could be longer – but this would mean extending the duration of the event.

Improvement suggestions for the future modules

Announcing a future module at department/ unit meetings would probably help increase the 'visibility' of the event.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

JSI's sub-page for Gender Equality: <https://www.ijs.si/ijsw/EnakostSpolov>

JSI Twitter:

https://twitter.com/JSI_SLO/status/1580883897465810944?cxt=HHwWgMCtuezhtvArAAAA

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Module 3: Work-life balance

General information

Venue	Jožef Stefan Institute, Great lecture hall
Date	25. 10. 2022 at 10:00
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Prof Dr Sara Tement
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Department of Psychology, Faculty of Arts, University of Maribor
Total number of participants	100
Number of high and middle managers participants	7
Number of HR professionals participants	NA
Number of professors and researchers participants	72
Number of administrative professionals participants	21
Number of students participants	NA
Total duration of the module (hours)	2,5
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Hybrid format (lecture room/Zoom)

Agenda

10.00 – 10.10: Gender equality at Jožef Stefan Institute, Dr Vida Vukašinović, JSI

10.10 – 10.45: Work-life balance

- Activity 1 + discussion: Identification of self-balancing work and private life

10.45 – 10.50: Break

10.50 – 11.35: Techniques to improve self-balancing of work and private life (employee's perspective)

- Activity 2 + discussion: Identification of negative thought patterns, related to work and work-life balance.

11.35 – 12.10: Techniques to improve self-balancing of work and private life (employer's and supervisor's perspective)

- Activity 3 + discussion: Identification of good organizational practices and discussion of implementation opportunities at JSI

12.10 – 12.15: Discussion and final thoughts

Event pictures

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Photo: Marjan Verč

Methodology and content

The module was designed as a lecture with time planned for active participation and discussion. Work-life balance was first defined. The absence of conflict is the layperson's understanding, so a special emphasis was put on the mutual enhancement of work and personal life. Several types of conflict and enhancement were described. In an interactive activity that followed, participants tried to identify characteristics of the work-private life relationship in their own lives and shared their findings if they wanted.

In the second part of the lecture, factors of work-life balance were presented. Here, the environment at different levels was taken into account: the legislation and broader culture that impact work-life balance; organizational policies, work conditions, and leadership; characteristics of personal life, such as familial relationships and friendships; and finally, individual characteristics, such as thoughts, emotions, and behaviours. This was followed by an activity in which participants tried to identify thought patterns that influence their work-life balance.

In the last part of the lecture, several organizational practices and policies were presented that can benefit employees' work-life balance. Among the prominently described were the right to disconnect, health circles, values and vision, leadership education, flexible work schedule and place of work, metrics of work productivity, human resources development etc.

Tools and techniques

The main tool of the lecture was a PowerPoint presentation. The activities were supported by worksheets that included questions that participants answered privately but could be shared with the group. The lecturer also invited thoughts and comments during these activities. Participants could get a turn by raising a hand and receiving a microphone so that online participants could also hear and participate in the discussion.

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Participants' feedback

During the interactive activities, participants shared their views on work-life balance. They pointed out familial obligations and how these sometimes conflict with the criteria for promotion at JSI. This can be a factor of gender inequality because of broader established gender roles, because of which women are expected to do most of the labour related to home life.

Some participants also emphasised other aspects of personal life, not necessarily related to family or having children. They pointed out that a lot of focus is put on having children when discussing this topic and not enough on other aspects, such as friendships, caring for elders, hobbies etc.

We also received an anonymous email following the module, in which a participant expressed her views on the topic and thanked us that we included it in the training programme.

Successes and difficulties

The main success of the module was that it invited a lot of discussions. The worksheets gave participants good starting points so that they could think about their own work-life balance. Some participants also felt comfortable enough to share these insights with the group, contributing to a more diverse representation of viewpoints. The main difficulty was timekeeping. The discussion sometimes needed to be cut short, but it might have been better to omit a slide or to in favour of the interactive parts. The whole module also ran well above the scheduled time.

A future module on this topic needs to pay attention to the balance between employees' (individual) perspectives and organizational and cultural factors of work-life balance. This was pointed out in the module but could be explored further. Work-life balance indeed includes our thoughts and behaviours that can be adapted, but some aspects are beyond employees' control and some others, such as legislation, beyond even the employer's control.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

JSI's sub-page for Gender Equality: <https://www.ijs.si/ijsw/EnakostSpolov>

JSI Twitter:

https://twitter.com/JSI_SLO/status/1584929125294227456?cxt=HHwWglCqtYyp5v4rAAAA

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Module 4: Ethics and integrity in research

General information

Venue	Jožef Stefan Institute, main lecture hall
Date	October 27, 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	1. Assoc. Prof. Dr Rok Benčin 2. Dr Jovana Mihajlovič Trbovc
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	ZRC SAZU Institute
Total number of participants	51
Number of high and middle managers participants	7
Number of HR professionals participants	NA
Number of professors and researchers participants	30
Number of administrative professionals participants	14
Number of students participants	NA
Total duration of the module (hours)	2 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Hybrid format (lecture room/Zoom)

Agenda

- Dr Ita Junkar, Gender Equality at Jožef Stefan Institute (introduction)
- Assoc. Prof. Dr Rok Benčin and Dr Jovana M. Trbovc, Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU), Ethics, integrity and gender equality in Slovenian and European research space (lecture)
- Break
- Dr Jovana M. Trbovc, ZRC SAZU, Guided discussion on gender equality in research (discussion led by the presenter)

Event pictures

Photo: Marjan Verč

Methodology and content

Content of the module

In the first part of the workshop the lecture by Assoc. Prof. Dr Rok Benčin was given, with

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inclusions from Jovana M. Trbovc. In this first part theoretical introduction was given, where ethics and integrity in the research were presented, also, data regarding regulatory issues and the reviewer process for evaluation of ethics in research for Horizon Europe projects were presented. The participants learned what are the basic principles and documents of research ethics and integrity. Assoc. Prof. Dr Rok Benčin presented the design and results of the currently ongoing CRP project "Ethics, integrity and gender equality in the research area of Slovenia: between policies and their implementation", which is being implemented at the Research Centre of the Slovenian Academy of Sciences and Arts (ZRC SAZU). At the end of the presentation, the ethical review process of research funded by the framework programs of the European Commission was presented. The lecturer also discussed the code of ethics and integrity in research which is valid for our institution and compared it to others. Inclusions in the lecture were made also by dr. Jovana M. Trbovc, where the emphasis was given to gender equality in research.

In the second part, a guided discussion took place, led by Dr Jovana M. Trbovec. In this part the following relevant topics for our institution were discussed:

- 1.) Scientific mobility from the perspective of gender
- 2.) Authorship and citations by gender
- 3.) Introducing the gender dimension in the composition of project groups

Practical examples and exercises were given to initiate discussions on the above-mentioned topics.

Tools and techniques

A PowerPoint presentation was used in the first part, together with data obtained from the CRP project: "Ethics, integrity and gender equality in the research area of Slovenia: between policies and their implementation". Case studies were used in the second part, which was mainly focused on gender equality in research.

Participants' feedback

The feedback from the participants was mainly that it is good to have this type of event, as so far in our institute we had mainly events dealing with research in natural sciences and techniques.

There was also a comment on ethics, and how important it is for the application of projects, especially for artificial intelligence, where different ethical questions arise. We've also received positive feedback regarding JSI's ethics protocol.

The discussion also raised questions about how women lose one year of research (not writing scientific papers, not going to conferences etc.) during maternity leave and how it influences their progression at work, how they are evaluated for promotion, how many tasks are given to other colleagues and how much harder is for them to get projects after a one-year absence from work.

We also discussed how male authors are cited more than women, and different opinions on this topic were raised; that those authors do not look if they cite male or female, that the higher number of citations can be due to the higher number of men leading the groups, etc.

We've received a suggestion for making our event more interactive by using tools like Mentimeter or question pro live polls.

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Successes and difficulties

Main success and difficulties related to this specific module

The module was of interest, as ethical issues were not yet presented at our institute; although we have an ethical codex on our internet webpage, most of the employees were unaware of its content nor of its existence. The guided discussion was a success as it enabled people to exchange opinions, especially regarding the obligatory postdocs that we have at our institute. The difficulty of the module was that it was organized in the same week as module 3, which was a bit too much, as for one week attending both workshops was hard.

Improvement suggestions for the future modules

Modules should not be organized so frequently, one per 2 weeks or one per week for 5 modules would be much better, but this time we had a short timeline due to the project deadlines. Improvements regarding workshops could be made by a more individual approach, by inviting people personally, especially motivating heads of department to promote workshops on this topic. Although we really tried to make good promotion; presenting workshop topics at departments, giving out flyers and invitations to all workers, and high support from our director (he was present at all five workshops and also invited lecturers to meet with him personally before the event, presented the topic at the meetings with the heads of departments etc.) the number of participants was still not as high as we would desire. After the events, the Athena coordinator at our institute received invitations from a few heads of departments to present GEPI at their departments. If such invitations or presentations were done before the workshops, we could increase the number of attendees. Still, from another point of view, this gives evidence that the modules also increased awareness from the heads of departments.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

JSI's sub-page for Gender Equality: <https://www.ijs.si/ijsw/EnakostSpolov>

JSI Twitter:

https://twitter.com/JSI_SLO/status/1585633430649573379?cxt=HHwWhsDQnYjNpoEsAAAA

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Module 5: Gender equality in career progression and recruitment

General information

Venue	Jožef Stefan Institute
Date	11. 11. 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	1.) Asst. Prof. Katarina Babnik 2.) Katja Dolinar 3.) Sindi Vogrič
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	1.) Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana 2.) Cosylab d.d. 3.) Cosylab d.d.
Total number of participants	98
Number of high and middle managers participants	12
Number of HR professionals participants	NA
Number of professors and researchers participants	62
Number of administrative professionals participants	24
Number of students participants	NA
Total duration of the module (hours)	2,5 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Hybrid format (lecture room/Zoom)

Agenda

10.00 - 10.05 Gender Equality and the Athena Project at the Jožef Stefan Institute, Prof. Dr Spomenka Kobe, JSI

10.05 - 10.50 Identifying existing gender imbalances and biases in recruitment and promotion in research organisations, Assoc. Prof. Dr Katarina Babnik, Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana

10.50 - 11.00 Break

11.00 - 11.20 Positive practices for overcoming gender inequalities in recruitment and promotion

- Implementation of the gender equality plan in the Cosylab Group, Katja Dolinar, Head of Human Resources, Cosylab d.d.

- Introduction of the Socially Responsible Employer certificate in the Cosylab Group, Sindi Vogrič, Cosylab d.d.

11.20 - 11.30 Questions and discussion

11.30 - 11.40 Presentation of the situation at the Jožef Stefan Institute regarding recruitment and career advancement opportunities, Luka Virag, JSI

11.40 - 12.00 Establishment of the Human Resources Management Unit at IJS, Assoc. Prof. Dr Katarina Babnik, Faculty of Arts, University of Ljubljana

12.00 - 12.15 Questions and discussion

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Event pictures

Photo: Marjan Verč

Methodology and content

Content of the module

The content of this module introduced the basic concepts of psychology and sociology of work related to ensuring gender equality in tertiary education, employment, and research (R&I). Therefore, the theoretical framework for understanding workforce diversity, which draws attention to various possible sources of inequality in the work environment at the level of individuals' personality characteristics and personal circumstances, as well as internal organisational and broader societal patterns, has been presented.

In the continuation, examples of good practices in Slovenia and the EU were presented to promote the inclusion of women in science and their career development in this field with recommended monitoring mechanisms and indicators.

The second part of the module addressed the fundamental role of the Human Resource (HR) unit in research and development, with a focus on ensuring workforce diversity and equality in recruitment, retention, and development. Emphasis has been placed on the required criteria for HR professionals and their role, as well as the role of leadership in a research institution. The HR function has been presented as a network of systems and recommended practices for managing people that complements and supports the management function in the organisation. It has also been emphasized that in ensuring gender equality, the HR function can only play a supporting role, while the key element in ensuring respect for and consideration of the diversity of the staff is assumed by the management function - the managers at all levels of the organisation.

Methodology

In the first part of the lecture, the theoretical part was presented and discussed, while in the second part example of an established HR unit in Cosylab company was presented and discussed.

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Tools and techniques

Main tools and techniques included:

- Lectures: PowerPoint presentations,
- Example of HR unit: PowerPoint presentation and discussion

Participants' feedback

The colleagues encourage the idea of establishing an HR unit at JSI. Such a unit should also be responsible for talent management, training and career development.

A female participant commented on the problem of promotions in case of extended absences such as maternity leave. Respective legislation, both on the levels of the institute and on the national level, allows extending the (vertical) promotion period for the duration of the maternity leave. However, in the case of horizontal promotion, the possibility of extended absences, such as maternity leave, is not considered (national legislation).

Another female colleague commented that the reasons for the differences between the genders, which are manifested in the different representation of women and men in certain professions, including science, as well as in career advancement, stem from the ways of raising children. Parenting and internal monologue are the main reasons for low self-esteem or to communicate confidently (with yourself and with others).

Another comment addressed the possibility of working part-time (fewer hours/day) due to parenthood. This could be a very good option for some parents who are chasing kindergarten schedules and commuting to more distant places. But as a logical consequence of a shorter working day, lower scientific production follows. This may consequently significantly influence (hinder) career progression and project applications. Many young parents decide to leave academic work and find employment in industry or elsewhere, where this condition is irrelevant.

Successes and difficulties

Main success and difficulties related to this specific module

- Very good response and cooperation with the invited lecturers during the process of forming the content of the module.
- New connections and backgrounds for further interdisciplinary knowledge exchange with external institutions were established.

Improvement suggestions for the future modules

- Find ways to engage more JSI participants, especially the unit leaders.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

JSI's sub-page for Gender Equality: <https://www.ijs.si/ijsw/EnakostSpolov>

3.2 UJK training programme

Training Topic: *Equal opportunities in science and research*

Module 1: Unconscious bias and its effects in the work environment

General information

Venue	Online
Date	27.10.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Kinga Di Carlo
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Diversity+
Total number of participants	54
Number of high and middle managers participants	1
Number of HR professionals participants	2
Number of professors and researchers participants	12
Number of administrative professionals participants	9
Number of students participants	30
Total duration of the module (hours)	2h
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	webinar

Numbers of representatives of mentioned about groups are estimated because UJK MS Teams doesn't have option to download attendance list. There is a print screen with the total number of participants and according to the registration list names/surnames has been check.

Agenda

Module 1: Unconscious bias in the workplace

- Diversity vs. differentiation. Basic framework of identity and categorization. Dimensions and consequences of (lack of) diversity in science and the academy.
- What are implicit biases? How do they affect our behaviour? Why is it so difficult to get rid of them? Exercises.
- What is an inclusive culture? How do we build it? Why is it so important for mitigating the effect of implicit bias?

Event pictures

Methodology and content

The content of the module covered topics:

- Mansfield Park: diversity vs. differentiation
- Inborn and acquired statuses.
- Types of statuses and their consequences
- Pride and prejudice: how much "implicit" prejudice is hidden and what is actually unconscious.
- Categorization processes
- Simplifying heuristics
- Cognitive cascade and control of judgment formulation and decision-making processes
- Reasoning and sensitivity: Why we need an inclusive culture in the workplace and learning environment.
- Unconscious biases vs. effectiveness
- Unconscious biases vs. meritocracy

Tools and techniques

The webinar was kept interactive. Participants had the opportunity to ask questions via chat, voice by hand and discussion after the meeting. In addition to the lecture, use cases, research results, examples were shown. Mentimeter.com was used to engage participants.

Participants' feedback

Participants thanked the valuable content and interesting form, dynamics of the trainer. The webinar was practical, many examples were presented, it was not boring.

There were some situations that participant didn't get link (sent 2 times) and asked for it when the webinar started. Participants will get information to check spam folder.

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Successes and difficulties

Around 55 participants took part it was success, but when we will notice that around 95 were registered it shows some challenge to overcome for organizers.
The training was registered so it will be disseminated to those who couldn't take part.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was fairly successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

All employees of UJK (academics, administrative, doctoral students, and students) got invitation from the **university general mailbox (1445 employees in all units and 11314 students)**.

Additional emailing to Administrative Departments was sent.

Information with registration for was available on the UJK main website:
<https://ujk.edu.pl/szkolenia.html>

FB groups (UJK students):
<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1598553117087272/posts/3553182768290954/>

FB groups (UJK in Kielce)
<https://www.facebook.com/groups/299976186696735/posts/6136905933003702/>

https://twitter.com/ATHENA_Equality/status/1585957748751024129

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/athena-equality_gender-unconsciousbias-activity-6991726415662452736-MjbK?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop

<https://www.facebook.com/ATHENAEquality/posts/pfbid02hB34pHbQk65j24xzJAxeLrt7hhNDmSYyQv7vxsN4LX137quStUH4J8Pjv2cMUiEpl>

Module 2: The gender dimension in research

- including gender issues in research

General information

Venue	online
Date	7.11.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Kinga Di Carlo
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Diversity+
Total number of participants	40
Number of high and middle managers participants	0
Number of HR professionals participants	2
Number of professors and researchers participants	15
Number of administrative professionals participants	8
Number of students participants	15
Total duration of the module (hours)	2h
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	webinar

Numbers of representatives of mentioned about groups are estimated because UJK MS Teams doesn't have option to download attendance list. There is a print screen with the total number of participants and according to the registration list names/surnames has been check.

Agenda

Module 2: Gender Perspective in Research

- What is the difference between "gender-blind" and "gender-sensitive" and "gender-specific" approaches? What do scientific studies that take into account both a sense of equity and the quality of results say?
- Is research quality related to gender? Diversity, gender and research excellence.
- Gender mainstreaming in science - when and how?

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Event pictures

Methodology and content

The content of the module covered topics:

- What is the difference between "gender-blind" and "gender-sensitive" and "gender-specific" approaches? What do scientific studies that take into account both a sense of equity and the quality of results say?
- Is research quality related to gender? Diversity, gender and research excellence.
- Gender mainstreaming in science - when and how?

Tools and techniques

The webinar was kept interactive. Participants had the opportunity to ask questions via chat, voice by hand and discussion after the meeting. In addition to the lecture, use cases, research results, examples were shown. Mentimeter.com was used to engage participants.

Participants' feedback

Participants thanked the valuable content and interesting form, dynamics of the trainer. The webinar was practical, many examples were presented, it was not boring.

Participants asked about additional materials and links. There were also questions about the certificates.

Successes and difficulties

Around 40 participants took part it was success, but when we will notice that around 80 were registered it shows some challenge to overcome for organizers, only a half took part actively.

The training was registered so it will be disseminated to those who couldn't take part.

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Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was fairly successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

All employees of UJK (academics, administrative, doctoral students, and students) got invitation from the **university general mailbox (1445 employees in all units and 11314 student)**

Additional emailing to Administrative Departments was sent.

Information with registration for was available on the UJK main website:

<https://ujk.edu.pl/szkolenia.html>

FB groups (UJK students):

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1598553117087272/posts/3553182768290954/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1598553117087272/posts/3567447563531141>

FB groups (UJK in Kielce)

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/299976186696735/posts/6136905933003702/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/299976186696735/posts/6186328844728077/>

Module 3: Equal opportunities and non-discrimination in research projects - universal project framework design

General information

Venue	online
Date	9.11.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Kinga Di Carlo
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Diversity+
Total number of participants	30
Number of high and middle managers participants	1
Number of HR professionals participants	4
Number of professors and researchers participants	14
Number of administrative professionals participants	5
Number of students participants	6
Total duration of the module (hours)	2h
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	webinar

Numbers of representatives of mentioned about groups are estimated because UJK MS Teams doesn't have option to download attendance list. There is a print screen with the total number of participants and according to the registration list names/surnames has been check.

Agenda

Module 3: Equal opportunities and non-discrimination in research projects

- Formal requirements for regional, national and international projects on equal opportunities and non-discrimination, including accessibility for people with disabilities. What to pay attention to and how to implement the principle of equal opportunities and non-discrimination.
- Horizontal and vertical approaches in defining equal opportunities in projects - methodologies.
- The principle of gender neutrality in the context of project and product and building balanced project teams.

Event pictures

Methodology and content

The content of the module covered topics:

- Formal requirements for regional, national and international projects on equal opportunities and non-discrimination, including guaranteed accessibility for people with disabilities. What to pay attention to, and how to implement the principle of equal opportunities and non-discrimination.
- Horizontal and vertical approaches in defining equal opportunities in projects - methodologies.
- The principle of gender neutrality in the context of project and product and building balanced project teams.

Tools and techniques

The webinar was kept interactive. Participants had the opportunity to ask questions via chat, voice by hand and discussion after the meeting. In addition to the lecture, use cases, research results, examples were shown. Mentimeter.com was used to engage participants. There were some questions according to technical project how to justify the equality.

Participants' feedback

Participants thanked the valuable content and interesting form, dynamics of the trainer. The webinar was practical, many examples were presented, it was not boring.

Participants asked about additional materials and links. There were also questions about the certificates.

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Successes and difficulties

Around 30 participants took part it was success, but when we will notice that around 80 were registered it shows some challenge to overcome for organizers.
The training was registered so it will be disseminated to those who couldn't take part.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was fairly successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

All employees of UJK (academics, administrative, doctoral students, and students) got invitation from the **university general mailbox - 1445 employees in all units and 11314 students and PhD students.**

Additional emailing to Administrative Departments was sent.

Information with registration for was available on the UJK main website:

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<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1598553117087272/posts/3567447563531141>

FB groups (UJK in Kielce)

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/299976186696735/posts/6136905933003702/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/299976186696735/posts/6186328844728077/>

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Module 4: Equality in career progression and recruitment

General information

Venue	online
Date	22.11.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Kinga Di Carlo
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Diversity+
Total number of participants	25
Number of high and middle managers participants	1
Number of HR professionals participants	8
Number of professors and researchers participants	7
Number of administrative professionals participants	8
Number of students participants	1
Total duration of the module (hours)	2h
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	webinar

Numbers of representatives of mentioned about groups are estimated because UJK MS Teams doesn't have option to download attendance list. There is a print screen with the total number of participants and according to the registration list names/surnames has been check.

Agenda

Module 4: Wanted, wanted - equality in career advancement and university recruitment.

Training plan:

- Formulation of expectations of competence, motivation and commitment - methods for identifying distortions based on stereotypes.
- Verbal and non-verbal determinants of status and identity - exercises.
- Cultural phenomena and their role in the process of formulating assessments - exercises.

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Event pictures

Methodology and content

The content of the module covered topics:

- My husband is a director by profession: Expectations of competence, motivation and commitment.
 - Processes that generate inequalities in recruitment and promotions
 - Homophily, fit, devaluation
 - Double standards vs. loaded evaluations (of performance/working people)
- Questions are biased: The broader context of recruitment, i.e., what can influence the decisions of potential applicants
 - Conscious and unconscious messages about the organization's culture
 - Language of recruitment
 - Recruitment interviews

Tools and techniques

The webinar was kept interactive. Participants had the opportunity to ask questions via chat, voice by hand and discussion after the meeting. In addition to the lecture, use cases, research results, examples were shown. Mentimeter.com was used to engage participants.

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Participants' feedback

Participants thanked the valuable content and interesting form, dynamics of the trainer. The webinar was practical, many examples were presented, it was not boring.

Participants asked about additional materials and links. There were also questions about the certificates.

Some questions appeared during discussion:

1. if every choice is discrimination, and every selection criterion is exclusionary, then should we be entitled to any, choices of anyone or anything - after all, statistics are based on the results of so-called objective studies
2. whether over-recruitment is not a case of discrimination and exclusion
3. do we necessarily have to equate everyone with everyone in all fields

Successes and difficulties

Around 25 participants took part it was success, but when we will notice that 82 were registered it shows some challenge to overcome for organizers.

The training was registered so it will be disseminated to those who couldn't take part.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was fairly successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

All employees of UJK (academics, administrative, doctoral students, and students) got invitation from the **university general mailbox - 1445 employees in all units and 11314 students and PhD students.**

Additional emailing to Administrative Departments was sent.

Information with registration for was available on the UJK main website:

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<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1598553117087272/posts/3567447563531141>

FB groups (UJK in Kielce)

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/299976186696735/posts/6136905933003702/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/299976186696735/posts/6186328844728077/>

Module 5: Inclusive language

General information

Venue	online
Date	29.11.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Kinga Di Carlo
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Diversity+
Total number of participants	67
Number of high and middle managers participants	2
Number of HR professionals participants	10
Number of professors and researchers participants	24
Number of administrative professionals participants	21
Number of students participants	10
Total duration of the module (hours)	2h
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	webinar

Numbers of representatives of mentioned about groups are estimated because UJK MS Teams doesn't have option to download attendance list. There is a print screen with the total number of participants and according to the registration list names/surnames has been check.

Agenda

Module 5: Inclusive language

Training plan:

- What are micro-communication, micro-inclusion or micro-aggressions? What are the most common forms of exclusion in formal and informal communication in research and at the university? Is "mansplaining" a microaggression?
- Individual, team and institutional sources of inequality in communication and language and their consequences.
- Identifying and neutralizing microaggressions and exclusionary language.

Event pictures

Methodology and content

The content of the module covered topics:

- What are micro-communication, micro-inclusion or micro-aggressions? What are the most common forms of exclusion in formal and informal communication in research and at the university? Is "mansplaining" a microaggression?
- Individual, team and institutional sources of inequality in communication and language and their consequences.
- Identifying and neutralizing microaggressions and exclusionary language.

Tools and techniques

The webinar was kept interactive. Participants had the opportunity to ask questions via chat, voice by hand and discussion after the meeting. In addition to the lecture, use cases, research results, examples were shown. Mentimeter.com was used to engage participants.

Participants' feedback

Participants thanked the valuable content and interesting form, dynamics of the trainer. The webinar was practical, many examples were presented, it was not boring.

Participants asked about additional materials and links. There were also questions about the certificates.

Successes and difficulties

67 participants took part it was success, but when we will notice that around 132 were registered it shows some challenge to overcome for organizers. The training was registered so it will be disseminated to those who couldn't take part.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was fairly successful.

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Links for the dissemination of the training

All employees of UJK (academics, administrative, doctoral students, and students) got invitation from the **university general mailbox - 1445 employees in all units and 11314 students and PhD students.**

Additional emailing to Administrative Departments was sent.

Information with registration for was available on the UJK main website:

<https://ujk.edu.pl/szkolenia.html>

FB groups (UJK students):

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<https://www.facebook.com/groups/1598553117087272/posts/3567447563531141>

FB groups (UJK in Kielce)

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/299976186696735/posts/6136905933003702/>

<https://www.facebook.com/groups/299976186696735/posts/6186328844728077/>

3.3 UB training programme

Training Topic: *A Gender Equal University: Beyond Stereotypes and Biases*

Module 1: Unconscious Bias

General information

Venue	Bucharest University, Hall 101, Panduri Street, Bucharest
Date	9/06/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Irina Costache
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Sircobo Advice SRL
Total number of participants	31
Number of high and middle managers participants	2
Number of HR professionals participants	5
Number of professors and researchers participants	0
Number of administrative professionals participants	26 (including HR professionals)
Number of students participants	2
Total duration of the module (hours)	4
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	In person training, interactive team-work based training

Agenda

June 9, time 12:00 -16:00

- *Introduction/Getting to know one another*
- *Education and Gender Equality*
- *Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*
- *Unconscious Bias, Prejudice, Stereotypes*
- *Gender Equality in the University of Bucharest (brief overview of ATHENA research findings)*
- *University of Bucharest - Gender Equality Plan*

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

This training module was structured around three main pillars:

- overview of gender equality, diversity and inclusion principles, definitions and impact on the education field
- overview of unconscious bias, its links with prejudice and stereotypes and strategies to overcome it
- overview of the state of play regarding gender equality at the University of Bucharest with findings from the ATHENA GEA research and a presentation of the UB's GEP developed under the ATHENA project

The agenda of the program included the following training points

- *Introduction/Getting to know one another*
- *Education and Gender Equality*
- *Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*
- *Unconscious Bias, Prejudice, Stereotypes*
- *Gender Equality in the University of Bucharest (brief overview of ATHENA research findings)*
- *University of Bucharest - Gender Equality Plan*

The methodology combined direct presentation with practical exercises and practical group activities. The focus of the activities designed was to encourage peer learning and to strengthen connections and teamwork among participants.

The group activities were the following:

- TAG GAME - creating diverse teams
- Gender Equality Conversations (card game with conversation starters for gender equality topics)
- Recognizing Bias - same person, two moments in the day
- Group work on activities and actions that consolidate GEP

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Tools and techniques

The training design included the design of a PPT presentation with a selection of the following:

- Stats on gender in the education field in RO
- Principles of Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion
- Legal norms governing GE, D&I
- Definitions and theories of unconscious bias
- selection of ATHENA research findings
- selection of GEP provision and structure

The group activities were the following:

- TAG GAME - creating diverse teams
- Gender Equality Conversations (card game with conversation starters for gender equality topics)
- Recognizing Bias - same person, two moments in the day
- Group work on activities and actions that consolidate GEP

At the end the participants were asked to fill in a feedback questionnaire as well as a knowledge-based test.

Participants' feedback

The participants rated the training with maximum points. Their most favourite feature of the training was the practical, activity-based approach included in the training.

The participants suggested having more training or activities on the topic of gender equality, They also suggested that the training must be offered to other professional groups in the university.

Most participants found the training useful for their current activities and welcomed the parts on unconscious bias, as well as the parts on the legal framework related to gender equality.

Participants consider that gender equality at the university is an important topic. Some made suggestions about improving gender equality in the university - such as to introduce topics and actions related to on women's health for administrative staff at the university - menopause support groups and rooms, etc. Other ideas related to gender equality trainings for incoming students and incoming teaching staff, more trainings on unconscious bias, etc.

Successes and difficulties

The main success of this training was that its content and its delivery not only matched participants expectations but exceeded them. Participants requested to participate in additional training on the topic.

The University Rector's Office proposed to offer the same training in fall for its administrative staff in order to give the chance to more participants to engage in the topic. The Athena team will deliver this training again in the fall. More requests for participation have been already received by ATHENA team.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

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Links for the dissemination of the training

<https://gep.unibuc.ro/athena/activitati/>

<https://unibuc.ro/s-a-dat-startul-inscrierilor-la-cursurile-destinate-personalului-didactic-auxiliar-si-nedidactic-al-universitatii-din-bucuresti/>

A notice is due in the University of Bucharest Newsletter for June 2022. The material will be sent out at the end of the month.

Module 1: Unconscious Bias (2)

General information

Venue	Bucharest University, Hall 101, Panduri Street, Bucharest
Date	20/10/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Irina Costache
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Sircobo Advice SRL
Total number of participants	25
Number of high and middle managers participants	3
Number of HR professionals participants	5
Number of professors and researchers participants	0
Number of administrative professionals participants	25 (including HR professionals)
Number of students participants	0
Total duration of the module (hours)	4
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	In person training, interactive teamwork based training

Agenda

October 20, time 9:00 -13:00

- *Introduction/Getting to know one another.*
- *Education and Gender Equality*
- *Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*
- *Unconscious Bias, Prejudice, Stereotypes*
- *Gender Equality in the University of Bucharest (brief overview of ATHENA research findings)*
- *University of Bucharest - Gender Equality Plan*

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

This training module was structured around three main pillars:

- overview of gender equality, diversity and inclusion principles, definitions and impact on the education field
- overview of unconscious bias, its links with prejudice and stereotypes and strategies to overcome it
- overview of the state of play regarding gender equality at the University of Bucharest with findings from the ATHENA GEA research and a presentation of the UB's GEP developed under the ATHENA project

The agenda of the program included the following training points

- *Introduction/Getting to know one another*
- *Education and Gender Equality*
- *Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*
- *Unconscious Bias, Prejudice, Stereotypes*
- *Gender Equality in the University of Bucharest (brief overview of ATHENA research findings)*
- *University of Bucharest - Gender Equality Plan*

The methodology combined direct presentation with practical exercises and practical group activities. The focus of the activities designed was to encourage peer learning and to strengthen connections and teamwork among participants.

The group activities were the following:

- TAG GAME - creating diverse teams
- Gender Equality Conversations (card game with conversation starters for gender equality topics)
- Recognizing Bias - same person, two moments in the day
- Group work on activities and actions that consolidate GEP

Tools and techniques

The training design included the design of a PPT presentation with a selection of the following:

- Stats on gender in the education field in RO
- Principles of Gender Equality, Diversity and Inclusion
- Legal norms governing GE, D&I
- Definitions and theories of unconscious bias
- selection of ATHENA research findings
- selection of GEP provision and structure

The group activities were the following:

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- TAG GAME - creating diverse teams.
- Gender Equality Conversations (playcard with conversation starters for gender equality topics)
- Recognizing Bias - same person, two moments in the day
- Group work on activities and actions that consolidate GEP.

At the end the participants were asked to fill in a feedback questionnaire as well as knowledge-based test.

Participants' feedback

The participants rated the training with maximum points. Their most favourite feature of the training was the practical approach included in the training. Participants rated high the group discussions and the play-card game on gender equality conversations. Participants also liked the examples and the role-play activities about gender stereotypes and unconscious bias.

The participants suggested having more training or activities on the topic of gender equality. Over 50% of participants suggested that they are willing to participate in other activities or trainings related to gender equality.

Most participants found the training useful for their current activities, appreciated the fresh information about gender stereotypes and the University of Bucharest Gender Equality Plan.

Participants consider that gender equality at the university is an important topic because there are some gender asymmetries that they noted in their own work. This group was particularly concerned with the work and life balance policies at the University of Bucharest. Many participants said that more needs to be done in order to transform the University into an organization/ an employer that truly delivers on its promise to provide a work environment concerned with life/work balance. Many participants mentioned the lack of childcare services as an impediment to achieve work life balance. One participant is in charge with compiling a sustainability report for the University and she offered to help with building synergies with other sustainability processes taking place in the University.

Successes and difficulties

The main success of this training was that its content and its delivery not only matched participants expectations but exceeded them. Participants requested to participate in additional training on the topic.

The University Rector's Office proposed to offer the same training in fall for its administrative staff in order to give the chance to more participants to engage in the topic. The Athena team will deliver this training again in the fall. More requests for participation have been already received by ATHENA team.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

<https://unibuc.ro/despre-ub/organizare/administratie/directia-resurse-umane/formarea-profesionala/>
<https://gep.unibuc.ro/egalitate-diversitate-incluziune-modul-2/>

Module 2: A Gender Equal University: Teaching beyond stereotypes and biases

General information

Venue	Bucharest University, Faculty of Sociology, 302
Date	26/10/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Irina Costache and Laura Grunberg, Athena project director
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Sircobo Advice SRL
Total number of participants	7
Number of high and middle managers participants	0
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	7
Number of administrative professionals participants	0
Number of students participants	0
Total duration of the module (hours)	2
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	1 in person training

Agenda

This training was held once and had a limited audience. Very few teaching staff showed interest in this training. In the future, other trainings will be also disseminated through the GEPI Committee Members to ensure visibility of the program.

October 26, time 18:00 -20:00

1. *Introduction/Getting to know one another.*
2. *Teaching and Gender – Facts and Figures*
3. *Unconscious bias and teaching materials*
4. *Teaching with out of the box examples and bibliographies*
5. *Gender Equality Plan – University of Bucharest a useful tool for UB teaching staff*

Event pictures

No pictures of the event were taken.

Methodology and content

This training module was structured around

- overview of teaching profession and gender
- overview of unconscious bias and how it manifests in teaching environments
- Teaching materials and gender stereotypes
- Teaching with out of the box examples
- Overview of the gender equality plan (PEG)

The agenda of the program included the following training points

Introduction/Getting to know one another

Teaching and Gender – Facts and Figures

Unconscious bias and teaching materials – special focus on manuals and course

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bibliographies

Teaching with out of the box – Group Activity

Gender Equality Plan – University of Bucharest a useful tool for UB teaching staff

The methodology combined direct presentation with examples and participatory activities. The focus of the examples and role play exercises was designed to encourage peer learning and to strengthen connections among participants.

The group activities were the following:

- Gender Attributes exercise
- Group discussions – For an inclusive curriculum – what ideas are there to improve the teaching curriculum
- Group discussion – Give examples of gendered language and illustrations from your teaching materials
- Group discussion – how do you think you can contribute to reaching GEP objectives?

Tools and techniques

The training design included the design of a PPT presentation with a selection of the following:

Gender stereotypes in Education and in teaching

Stats from the Gender Equality Audit on where women in the University of Bucharest work; what positions and what levels of seniority

Categories of analysis for the teaching materials and gender; where can gender stereotypes emerge and how can they be corrected

selection of GEP provision and structure

The group activities were the following:

At the beginning of the session participants were asked to give gendered attributes to two characters, then they were asked to use the characteristics using a male and a female character and to see where the attributes they found don't work or don't match. The aim of the exercise is to show that apart from a few biological characteristics, all the other gendered characteristics can apply to both female and male characters.

Then during the course there were the following group activities:

For an inclusive curriculum – what ideas are there to improve the teaching curriculum

Group discussion – Give examples of gendered language and illustrations from your teaching materials

Group discussion – how do you think you can contribute to reaching GEP objectives?

Due to the small group of participants, at the end the participants were asked to provide feedback orally.

Participants' feedback

The participants said that the training was useful and that more colleagues should participate in a training on gender equality. The participants appreciated the most the time and the activities aimed at strengthening self – reflection. The participants also said that more research projects should be encouraged in the area of gender and teaching materials/curricula development/ teaching methods/bibliographies. In fact, each faculty within the University of Bucharest should try and develop its own interdisciplinary research projects focused on gender.

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Successes and difficulties

The main challenge of this training was to find teaching staff interested in attending a training. Most of the teaching staff has full teaching schedules and have little interest to participate in events which are outside of their disciplines and outside of their workload. Unfortunately, this training had few attendees but for the future, a different dissemination strategy should be put in place, one that involves GEPI Committee members. The training was held during a meeting of a newly formed gender interdisciplinary research platform. The main success of the training was that the participants showed a real interest in the topic and remained connected and said they will communicate ideas and recommend the training to other teaching staff.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was successful but there was a very low turnout rate

Links for the dissemination of the training

N/A

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Module 3: A Gender Equal University: useful concepts for students

General information

Venue	Bucharest University, Faculty of Journalism, Main Building R3
Date	25/11/2022 and 29/11/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Irina Costache
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Sircobo Advice SRL
Total number of participants	60
Number of high and middle managers participants	0
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	0
Number of administrative professionals participants	0
Number of students participants	60
Total duration of the module (hours)	2
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	1 - in person training and 1 online training

Agenda

This training was held twice due to a demand from the Faculty of Journalism. The first time on 25/11/2022 in person for 3rd year students and the second time online on the 29/11/2022 for second year students. At the first training no pictures were taken due to a technical error.

November 25, time 10:00 -12:00

- *Introduction/Getting to know one another*
- *Gender Equality and Higher Education Graduates: Facts and Figures*
- *Gender stereotypes – what they are and how they influence students*
- *Playing the Gender Equality Game – Conversation starters (interactive part using a gender equality card game) – for the online module the card*
- *Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest*

November 29, time 16:00 -18:00

- *Introduction/Getting to know one another*
- *Gender Equality and Higher Education Graduates: Facts and Figures*
- *Gender stereotypes – what they are and how they influence students*
- *Playing the Gender Equality Game – Conversation starters (interactive part using a gender equality card game) – for the online module the card*
- *Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest*

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Event pictures

Methodology and content

This training module was structured around two main pillars:

- overview of gender equality and higher education
- overview of gender stereotypes, unconscious bias, its links with educational and career choices for students
- The impact of gender inequality in the life of students – by using a card game
- Overview of the gender equality plan (PEG)

The agenda of the program included the following training points

- *Introduction/Getting to know one another*
- *Gender Equality and Higher Education Graduates: Facts and Figures*
- *Gender stereotypes – what they are and how they influence students*
- *Playing the Gender Equality Game – Conversation starters (interactive part using a gender equality card game) – for the online module the card*
- *Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest*

The methodology combined direct presentation with practical exercises and practical group activities. The focus of the activities designed was to encourage peer learning and to strengthen connections and teamwork among participants.

The group activities were the following:

- Gender Equality Conversations play-card with conversation starters for gender equality topics)
- Group work what activities can students do to promote gender equality in the University?

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Tools and techniques

The training design included the design of a PPT presentation with a selection of the following:

- Stats on gender in the education field in RO
- Definitions stereotypes, unconscious bias
- Selection of GEP provision and structure

The group activities were the following:

- Gender Equality Conversations (play-card with conversation starters for gender equality topics)
- Group work on activities and actions that consolidate GEP

At the end the participants were asked to fill in a feedback questionnaire

Participants' feedback

The participants rated the training with maximum points. Their most favourite feature of the training was the practical approach included in the training. Participants rated high the group discussions and the play-card game on gender equality conversations.

Over 70% of participants suggested that they are willing to participate in other activities or trainings related to gender equality.

Most participants found the training useful and said that this is the first time they discuss gender equality in a university setting. Students said that there is a lot to be done to improve gender equality in Romanian society and that more can be done to improve gender equality in the university too. Students said that gender inequality is mostly manifested in student-student interactions, but some also mentioned that they feel treated differently in the university due to their belonging to one gender. Students also said that gender equality and gender-based violence are not topics that usually addressed at a University level but that they discuss about gender equality informally. They also mentioned that in primary and secondary school teachers sometimes treated unequally girls and boys. Girls were often encouraged to think of careers where they would require doing more emotional labour or where they would express their care-ing side – such as teaching, being a journalist, doctor or social worker.

Successes and difficulties

The main challenge of this training was to get students to participate outside of their regular classes schedule. There have been several attempts to communicate about this training to students, but we were only able to gather a consistent group of participants once ATHENA team asked GEPI members to recommend this class to their students. No interest in the course from the Student's Associations.

The main success of this training was that once students participated, they become involved and evaluate the training as useful for their professional development. They also said that during the training they learned new information that they will use beyond the university environment.

Another success of this training was that students from the Faculty of Journalism requested this training twice – once for third year students and once for second year students (this one was held online as requested per students).

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Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

<https://gcp.unibuc.ro/atelier-egalitate-studenti/>

Module 4: Preventing Gender Based Violence: recognize it and act

General information

Venue	Bucharest University, Faculty of Sociology, 302
Date	16/11/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Irina Costache
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Sircobo Advice SRL
Total number of participants	20
Number of high and middle managers participants	0
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	0
Number of administrative professionals participants	0
Number of students participants	20
Total duration of the module (hours)	2
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	1 in person training

Agenda

This training was held twice due to a demand from the Faculty of Journalism. The first time on 25/11/2022 in person for 3rd year students and the second time online for second year students.

November 16, time 16:00 -18:00

6. *Introduction/Getting to know one another*
7. *Gender based violence – facts and figures*
8. *Main types of gender-based violence in the University*
9. *Examples of youth led campaigns against gender-based violence*
10. *Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest*

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

This training module was structured around two main pillars:

- overview of gender-based violence – facts and figures
- overview of main types of gender-based violence in the university – also indication of where students can find support
- Role play and examples
- Youth led campaigns against gender-based violence
- Overview of the gender equality plan (PEG)

The agenda of the program included the following training points

Introduction/Getting to know one another

Gender based violence – facts and figures

Main types of gender-based violence in the University

Examples of youth led campaigns against gender-based violence

Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest

The methodology combined direct presentation with examples and role play exercises. The focus of the examples and role play exercises was designed to encourage peer learning and to strengthen connections and teamwork among participants.

The group activities were the following:

- Gender Light Bulb Exercise
- Examples of GBV in the university and role play
- Group work what campaign would you do to end GBV in the University?

Tools and techniques

The training design included the design of a PPT presentation with a selection of the following:

- Stats on gender-based violence in RO
- Definitions of forms of GBV in the University, particular focus on sexual harassment in the Uni
- selection of GEP provision and structure

The group activities were the following:

Gender Light Bulb

Example's – what would you do if you were X's friend

Ending GBV in the University

At the end the participants were asked to fill in a feedback questionnaire

Participants' feedback

The participants said that the training was very useful especially that they have never attended a training on GBV. The students were positively impressed that the University was supporting this type of course. Many students said that before this training they believed GBV was a private matter not of interest to the University. They appreciated the information related to support services that exist within the University and many said that they didn't know about these services.

They rated the training with maximum points. Their most favourite feature of the training was the information related to psychological counselling and channels of complaint for students (which they can use also for GBV incidents). Even if at this point the University doesn't have a channel for GBV specific incidents, still students were not aware of the existing channels of petition and complaint.

Most participants found the training very useful and that the information discussed in this training is useful beyond the academic setting. Students also rated as excellent the performance of the trainer.

Successes and difficulties

The main challenge of this training was to get students to participate outside of their regular classes schedule. There have been several attempts to communicate this training to students, but we were only able to gather a consistent group of participants once ATHENA team asked GEPI members to recommend this class to their students.

The main success of this training was that once students participated, they become involved and evaluate the training as useful for their professional development.

Another success of this training was that the University Student Relationship Office has asked ATHENA staff and consultant to design an online training on Diversity, Inclusion, Prevention of Sexual Harassment within the University. The plan is for this course to be part of the onboarding process of new students at the University of Bucharest. Expected launch of the project – Spring 2023.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

N/A

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Module 5: Mainstreaming Gender in Inter-disciplinary Academic Research

General information

Venue	Bucharest University, Faculty of Sociology, 302
Date	27/01/2023
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Irina Costache
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Sircobo Advice SRL
Total number of participants	38
Number of high and middle managers participants	0
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	38
Number of administrative professionals participants	0
Number of students participants	0
Total duration of the module (hours)	2
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	1 in person training

Agenda

This training was held twice due to a demand from the Faculty of Journalism. The first time on 25/11/2022 in person for 3rd year students and the second time online for second year students.

January 27, time 16:00 -18:00

11. Introduction
12. Gender Mainstreaming in Academic Research
13. Examples of Gender Mainstreaming in Research Projects at the University of Bucharest
14. Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest
15. Moderated Discussion on Gender Mainstreaming in current research projects led by participants.

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

This training module was structured around two main pillars:

- overview of gender mainstreaming in interdisciplinary academic research
- Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest

The agenda of the program included the following training points:

Introduction

Gender Mainstreaming in Academic Research

Gender Equality Plan of the University of Bucharest

Moderated Discussion about mainstreaming gender in research projects

The methodology combined direct presentation with discussion on the practicalities and advantages of introducing gender mainstreaming in academic research.

The group activities were the following:

- *Moderated Discussion on Gender Mainstreaming in current research projects led by participants*

Tools and techniques

The training design included the design of a PPT presentation with a selection of the following:

- Gender Mainstreaming in Academic Research
- Examples of research projects with a gender mainstreaming approach
- Selection of GEP provision regarding gender equality in research

The group activities were the following:

A moderated discussion on gender mainstreaming in the current research projects conducted by PhD students and early career researchers present at the training.

At the end the participants were asked to fill in a feedback questionnaire.

Participants' feedback

The participants said that the training was very useful mostly because this training session was the first opportunity current PhD and early career researchers had to discuss about gender mainstreaming and the approach to introducing gender in their research projects. Participants said that they want additional opportunities to discuss their research projects and possible gender lenses they could use in their research. Participants also said that they would be interested in accessing more academic literature on gender mainstreaming in research design.

The participants found useful the presentation points related to the GEP and its objective on research (objective no.7), as many were not aware of the existence of a gender equality plan at the University of Bucharest. Some participants said they would be interested in participating in the informal network of gender researchers set up at the University of Bucharest.

They rated the training with maximum point and most participants found the training as very useful. Students also rated as excellent the performance of the trainer.

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Successes and difficulties

The main challenge of this training was to get participants to enrol in this training. As a solution to mitigate the risk of non-participation, this training module was included in another longer training framework on Academic Ethics for PhD and early career researchers at the University of Bucharest. Therefore, the training was also delivered later than initially scheduled. The majority of the training participants were engaged in research projects at the departments of Sociology, Psychology, Educational Studies and Philosophy.

The main success of the training was that current PhD and Early career researchers showed interest in participating in other activities outlined in the Gender Equality Plan.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

N/A

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3.4 ULPGC training programme

Training Topic: *Advancing towards gender equality at the ULPGC*

**Module 1: Leadership and career
progression in the company**

General information

Venue	Faculty of Economics, Business and Turism of University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Date	11 th of November of 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Carolina Mesa Marrero, Beatriz González Lopez-Valcarcel and Marina Elistratova Elistratova
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Total number of participants	26
Number of high and middle managers participants	1
Number of HR professionals participants	
Number of professors and researchers participants	4
Number of administrative professionals participants	
Number of students participants	21
Total duration of the module (hours)	2:30 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Face-to-face

Agenda

- *Welcome (15 min)*
- *Gender inequalities among young professionals in Spain. The case of economy and business (45 minutes)*
- *Benefits of a greater presence of women on the boards of directors of companies (45 minutes)*
- *Workshop on advance proposals and conclusion of the contributions of the participations of the attendees (40 minutes)*
- *Closure (5 minutes)*

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

The lectures combine theoretical exposition with the development of examples and practices individual and group, especially focused on the experiences of not only the researchers but also using data from the National Institute of Statistics to expose and debate it in the face-to-face session on the last day. Digital resources and updated publications were used, as well as database from official sites and websites, from national and international resources.

Module: Leadership and professional progression in the company:

1. Framework presentation: "Inequality in the development of professional careers for women" (carried out simultaneously for the three workshops)
2. Leadership styles in the company
3. Experiences in female leadership
4. Advance proposals
5. Conclusions. Summary and proposals.

Preferred target group: university students, notwithstanding that other members of the university community may attend as long as capacity allows.

Tools and techniques

As for the tools, the room in which it was carried out had a projector machine and a sound system conditioned so that there would be no problem in hearing each other. The speakers used power point presentations as a tool to present their data and programs.

Likewise, the speakers, using the indicated tools, carried out the training face-to-face. This allowed the attendees to participate so that they could present ideas and opinions.

Participants' feedback

The comments were developed at the end of the presentations of the speakers, where the students, professors and researchers presented their opinions on the issues raised, their own experience and a debate was generated on how the new generations can contribute to the elimination of gender barriers in the field of the private enterprise.

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Successes and difficulties

The main success of the course has been the involvement in learning and participation of the students and the rest of attendees, who from each of their own experiences and point of views contributed to the debate, and shared experiences and ask many questions on how to reduce barriers in gender equality.

The main difficulty of the trainee was having few professors from the ULPGC and few researchers. For future occasions, we will improve the dissemination of the event to these people or offer them options that are more attractive: such as certificate of participation, compensation of working hours, etc.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

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Module 2: Leadership and career progression in public administration

General information

Venue	Faculty of Economics, Management and Tourism – ULPGC University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Date	11 th of November of 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Jimena Delgado Taramano
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria and Gobierno de Canarias
Total number of participants	17
Number of high and middle managers participants	2
Number of HR professionals participants	
Number of professors and researchers participants	3
Number of administrative professionals participants	
Number of students participants	12
Total duration of the module (hours)	2 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Face-to-face

Agenda

- Welcome (15 minutes)
- Leadership and professional progression in the public sector (1 hour)
- Workshop on advance proposals and conclusion of the contributions of the participations of the attendees (40 minutes)
- Closure (5 minutes)

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

The conference presented by Jimena Delgado Taramona, a political figure of the Canary Islands Government and with an extensive experience in the public sector, used as a methodology an exposition of the reasons why she decided to access public jobs and her interest in politics. She did a presentation about what it has meant for her to be a woman in high job categories and political personnel in the Public Administration and the differences she finds in terms of gender equality in politics, the public sector and private companies.

Module: Leadership and career progression in public administration

1. Framework paper: "Inequality in the development of women's professional careers" (develops simultaneously for the three workshops)
2. Leadership styles in public administration
3. Experiences in female leadership
4. Progress proposals
5. Conclusions. Summary and proposals.

Preferred target group: university students, without prejudice to the fact that other members of the university community can attend as long as capacity allows.

Tools and techniques

As for the tools, the room in which it was carried out had a projector machine and a sound system conditioned so that there would be no problem in hearing each other. However, the speaker did not use these materials and did not use any power point presentations or online database. She talked about her experience in the public administration.

Likewise, the speaker, using the indicated tools, carried out the training face-to-face. This allowed the attendees to participate so that they could present ideas and opinions.

Participants' feedback

The comments were developed at the end of the presentations of the speakers, where the students, professors and researchers presented their opinions on the issues raised, their own experience and a debate was generated on how the new generations can contribute to the elimination of gender barriers in the field of the public sector, but mostly, in politics.

Successes and difficulties

The main success of the course has been the involvement in learning and participation of the students and the rest of attendees, who from each of their own experiences and point of views contributed to the debate, and shared experiences and ask many questions on how to reduce barriers in gender equality.

The only drawback we have encountered is the public's lack of interest in accessing the public administration. In Spain, it is more common for people who study law to be interested in accessing the public system, so it is suggested that for future occasions go to law students and not economics, business and tourism.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Module 3: Leadership and professional progression in research

General information

Venue	Faculty of Economics, Management and Tourism – ULPGC
Date	11 th of November of 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Carolina Mesa Marrero, Carmen Grau Pineda
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Total number of participants	15
Number of high and middle managers participants	1
Number of HR professionals participants	
Number of professors and researchers participants	4
Number of administrative professionals participants	
Number of students participants	10
Total duration of the module (hours)	2 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Face-to-face

Agenda

- Welcome (15 minutes)
- The importance of equality plans as a tool to move towards effective equality in the framework of research (1 hour)
- Workshop on advance proposals and conclusion of the contributions of the participations of the attendees (40 minutes)
- Closure (5 minutes)

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

The lecture combine theoretical exposition with the development of examples and practices individual and group, especially focused on the experiences of not only the researchers but also using data from the National Institute of Statistics to expose and debate it in the face-to-face session on the last day. Digital resources and updated publications were used, as well as database from official sites and websites, from national and international resources.

Module: "Leadership and professional progression in research"

1. Framework presentation: "Inequality in the development of professional careers for women" (carried out simultaneously for the three workshops)
2. Research leadership styles
3. Female leadership experiences
4. Advance Proposals
5. Conclusions. Summary and proposals.

Preferred target group: university students, notwithstanding that other members of the university community may attend as long as capacity allows.

Tools and techniques

As for the tools, the room in which it was carried out had a projector machine and a sound system conditioned so that there would be no problem in hearing each other. The speakers used power point presentations as a tool to present their data and programs. Likewise, the speakers, using the indicated tools, carried out the training face-to-face. This allowed the attendees to participate so that they could present ideas and opinions.

Participants' feedback

The comments were developed at the end of the presentations of the speakers, where the students, professors and researchers presented their opinions on the issues raised, their own experience and a debate was generated on how the new generations can contribute to the elimination of gender barriers in the field of the research field.

Successes and difficulties

The main success of the course has been the involvement in learning and participation of the students and the rest of attendees, who from each of their own experiences and point of views contributed to the debate, and shared experiences and ask many questions on how to reduce barriers in gender equality.

The main difficulty we have encountered has been that we have lacked a research speaker from the field of STEM, who would have enriched the training.

As for suggestions, for the future we will try to expand communication with different professionals and researchers to invite them to the event.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Module 4: Prevention and action against gender- based violence

General information

Venue	Faculty of Law of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Date	03/11/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Eloy José Naranjo Perera
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Police Department of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Total number of participants	59
Number of high and middle managers participants	
Number of HR professionals participants	
Number of professors and researchers participants	2
Number of administrative professionals participants	
Number of students participants	57
Total duration of the module (hours)	2:15 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Face-to-face

Agenda

- Welcome (15 minutes)
- Gender-based violence and new technologies (1 hour)
- Debate: Prevention and action against gender violence (45 minutes)
- Closure (15 minutes)

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

The lectures combine theoretical exposition with the development of examples and practices, especially focused on the experiences of the police department in gender-based violence real cases.

Regarding the theoretical part of the lecture, the different types of gender violence were explained (physical abuse, psychological abuse, economic abuse and sexual abuse) and the different problems related to new technologies and gender violence, and its consequences on victims of violence, were discussed.

The lecture especially focused on events and real cases of gender violence that the police department of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria has encountered.

Likewise, the different protocols that must be followed in this type of situation were explained and the tools that can help to alleviate this type of violent situation were shown.

Module: "Prevention and action against gender violence"

1. Identification of myths and stereotypes in gender violence
2. Know the Spanish legislative framework on gender violence and its practical application
3. The different forms of violence against women and their impact.

Preferred target group: law degree students, without prejudice to the fact that other university students may attend as long as capacity allows.

Tools and techniques

As for the tools, the room in which it was carried out had a projector machine and a sound system conditioned so that there would be no problem in hearing the speaker. The speaker used a power point presentation as a tool to present their lecture.

Likewise, the speakers, using the indicated tools, carried out the training face-to-face. This allowed the attendees to participate so that they could present ideas and opinions.

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Participants' feedback

The comments developed at the end of the presentations of the speakers. The students and professors of Law of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria presented their opinions on the issues raised, their own experience and a debate was generated on how the new generations can contribute to the elimination of gender barriers by using correctly the new technologies. For this reason, the attendees placed special emphasis on how the correct use of new technologies should be and asked about the necessary tools for it.

In addition, the public questioned essential aspects of gender violence, such as the one exerted on women for the mere fact of being women. Likewise, they expressed doubts about gender equality being a formally achieved human right, but not in reality, since they considered that this type of statement is due to political and partisan purposes that only show part of the data.

Successes and difficulties

The main success of the course has been the involvement in learning and participation of the students and the rest of attendees, who from each of their own experiences and point of views contributed to the debate, and shared experiences and ask many questions about the different type of violence and how new technologies can increase cases of gender violence.

We believe this topic is a transversal issue that should have reached most of the students of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, and not only law students. For this reason, we are going to consider doing it as a combined session, face-to-face and online, in future occasions.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Module 5: Methodologies applied to gender studies in the humanities and social sciences

General information

Venue	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.
Date	24 th , 25 th , 26 th of May and 1 st of June.
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Pilar Dominguez Prats and Carmen Ascanio Sánchez
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) and University of La Laguna (ULL)
Total number of participants	4
Number of high and middle managers participants	
Number of HR professionals participants	
Number of professors and researchers participants	2
Number of administrative professionals participants	
Number of students participants	2
Total duration of the module (hours)	25 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Face-to-face lesson and online lesson.

Agenda

24/05/2022 – Origins and development of feminist social studies and the gender approach (relationship between feminism and research). How to make women visible: methodologies and techniques I (3 hours)

25/05/2022 – How to make women visible: methodologies and techniques II (3 hours).

26/05/2022 – The social sciences: methodologies and gender approach (3 hours).

01/06/2022 – Working on an interdisciplinary research case (3 hours).

24/05/2022 – 01/06/2022 –Self-study (9 hours) and online activities (4 hours).

Event pictures

24/05/2022 – Face-to-face lecture:

01/06/2022 – Online lecture:

Methodology and content

Methodology:

The lectures combine theoretical exposition with the development of examples and practices individual and group, especially focused on a practical case that is present in face-to-face classes and that the students will develop in groups, to expose and debate it in the online session on the last day. Digital resources and updated publications were used.

Content:

1. Women, leading subjects in the new social and cultural history.
2. How to make gender visible: methodologies and historical interpretation.
 - 2.1 The sources of memory and its methodology.
 - 2.2 Oral stories and photography.
3. Example of gender research on the recent past.
4. The social sciences: methodologies and gender approach.
5. Methodologies, techniques and tools: perspectives, speeches and interpretation.

Fieldwork: collective memories, types of observation, interviews. The vision analysis.

6. Studies and examples for reflection (social sciences).
7. Working on an interdisciplinary research case (individual or group work):

Gender equality in universities: Evolution, representation and structures.

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Tools and techniques

- Exhibitions of various methodologies used in the humanities and social sciences; specifically, several case studies based on investigations of the teachers. Through them, approaches and processes are described to make visible the gender, as well as the most appropriate methodologies for the objectives of each case study.
- The practice has focused on a research design, in the disciplines of each participant, where to adjust to the most appropriate methodology and techniques for the intended objectives. In these cases, some tools has been explained for the particular use.
- To elaborate the final practice, the steps and results of the “CIMPI” project on equality policies were pointed out. Through these policies, the participants have been asked to prepare and present a project design with gender perspective, applying the methodologies they consider most convenient. This was done on the last day of the online class and is the basis for the qualification of the course participants.

Participants’ feedback

The comments were developed especially in the last practical session where the students presented their research designs and positively valued learning to analyze research with a gender perspective and the adaptation of methodologies to their fields of analysis

Successes and difficulties

The main success of the course has been the involvement in learning of the students, who from each of their disciplines have contributed their baggage and their methodological doubts.

Regarding the weaknesses of the course, we would point out the lack of attendance of many of the people enrolled, which has limited the exchange of experiences from different areas, as well as the formation of work groups.

Regarding the number of attendees, the ULPGC gave the enough diffusion and dissemination to the event to enroll the maximum number of students, which was 20. The main problem was that the first phase of the training was a face-to-face session so, for this reason, many of these students did not attend.

Therefore, we believe that one of the aspects to improve for future sessions would be carrying out training in a hybrid way (face-to-face and online). This way, we could avoid that some of the students who applied and were accepted to participate in the training, may attend in the format that best suits their needs.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was fairly successful.

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Module 6: Human rights and gender equality

General information

Venue	Lecture room of the Faculty of Legal Sciences of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Date	12/12/22
Full name of the expert conducting the training	1. Ana Lydia Fernández -Layos 2. Yaiza Gomez Yanez
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	1. Ana Lydia Fernández - Layos is the director of the association Optiónate 2. Yaiza Gómez Yánez is an Athena technical staff of the Equality Unit of the ULPGC
Total number of participants	100
Number of participants from middle and senior management	2
Number of participating HR professionals	
Number of participating professors and researchers	3
Number of participating administrative professionals	
Number of participating students	95
Total duration of the module (hours)	2:10 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	face-to-face classroom lesson

Agenda

- Welcome (15 minutes) Carolina Mesa Marrero- Director of the Equality Unit of the ULPGC and IP of the Athena project of the ULPGC. Desiderio J. García Almeida- Director of Cooperation of the ULPGC
- Being born a girl: a vital and global risk. (35min) by Ana Lydia Fernández -Layos
- Care: essential for sustaining life and an obstacle to real equality for women. (35min)by Yaiza Gómez Yánez
- Debate: Equality for women today (30min)
- Closure and conclusions (15 min) Guacimara Gil Sánchez- Research Professor at the ULPGC-

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

The lectures combined theoretical presentations of a conceptual type and presentation of data to justify the claims. Practical examples from daily life were used to facilitate understanding of the theory.

The first conference explained the different challenges faced by girls and women around the world, and how human rights protect them in theory but not in practice. Examples were used such as: the slavery and servitude of girls, forced marriages, female genital mutilation, clandestine abortions, and human trafficking, especially in the field of prostitution.

In the second conference, they discussed the care work carried out by women in the world and how this implies inequality and discrimination for them. The roles and stereotypes that exist about women caregivers were discussed, and how this is linked to nature, and yet it is a cultural and historical construction. It was also suggested that care is an essential activity for sustaining life and is important for our human existence, but it generates inequality when only half the world (women) perform it and generally for free.

In the debate we worked on the information of the presentations. There was talk about how this affects the daily life of women, but it goes unnoticed because many people believe that we already have achieved equality between men and women. It was explained that the difference between formal and real equality is what prevents women, even though they have recognized rights, from being able to put them into practice due to these external conditioning factors of a cultural, historical, customs or tradition nature.

Tools and techniques

As for the tools, the room in which it was carried out had a projector machine and a conditioned sound system so that there would be no problem hearing the speakers. The speakers used a power presentation point as a tool to present your conference.

Likewise, the speakers, using the indicated tools, carried out face-to-face training. This allowed the participation of the attendees so that they could present ideas and opinions.

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Participants' feedback

The students participated in the final debate explaining their opinions and experience with the issues raised. A debate was generated, and they thought that equality was something already achieved. After the presentations of the papers, they were able to verify that this is not the case in all parts of the world.

The students were impressed with the reality that forced marriages currently exist and that women and girls around the world carry out care work that prevents them from going to school and prevents them from carrying out their own life projects because they are conditioned by these strong gender roles.

Successes and difficulties

The greatest success of this training has been to make students aware of the need to continue working on the equality of women and men.

It was possible to generate an interesting debate with different positions that helps to create critical thinking in the students. We believe that this is important so that they can combat the misinformation that exists in many media about equality.

We believe that the high participation and high interest in the subject allows us to reconsider this activity in the future with other types of students, with the aim of reaching the largest possible number of participants.

An improvement for the future will be to do it for students of different degrees in a larger room and with a good schedule that allows them to attend. We also think that it would be positive to link it with some benefit from the ULPGC for the attendees, such as credits in the subjects.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

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3.5 UVSK SAV training programme

Training Topic: *Gender Equality in Science*

Module 1: Introduction to Gender Equality

General information

Venue	Zoom
Date	13 May 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Ľubica Rozborová
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	RISOTO, subcontracted by UVSK SAV
Total number of participants	27
Number of high and middle managers participants	3
Number of HR professionals participants	NA
Number of professors and researchers participants	11 (together with 1 GEPI member and 2 members from the Ethical committee)
Number of administrative professionals participants	5
Number of students participants	8
Total duration of the module (hours)	3
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Zoom webinar with discussion

Agenda

2 hours: Lecture with videos and examples

1 hour: Discussion, Q&A

Trainer: Ľubica Rozborová (external gender experts)

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

Module 1: Introduction to Gender Equality

- 1.) What is gender. Gender inequalities
- 2.) Gender bias
- 3.) Horizontal and vertical segregation
- 4.) Individual strategies to address gender inequalities.
- 5.) Gender Equality Plan and its role in addressing gender inequalities.

Target group: researchers and administrative staff (wider target)

This module aimed to provide participants the basic information on GE. Our gender expert, Ľubica Rozborová provided a wide variety of theoretical information on: gender/sex terminology, gender socialization, gender roles, expectations, horizontal and vertical segregation, glass ceiling, glass elevator and gender in institutions. Finally, we discussed possible individual or structural strategies how to combat gender inequalities.

Tools and techniques

Zoom meeting was held using:

- Presentations with videos
- Discussion format
- Materials on best practice and examples

Participants' feedback

Participants had several questions on quotas, how to promote GE in institution, how to promote cultural and institutional change. Participants also share their views on the issue, and we see a great potential that these participants may become a multiplier of the presented issues.

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Successes and difficulties

The first challenge we have faced is the issue of training promotions. There is no internal platform where we can distribute information of training offers. Therefore, we spent hours in individual invitations to higher management and other internal stakeholders, asking to share information on trainings among their employees. We have also published information on SAS website.

Overall, we were excited that in spite of difficulties in recruitment for trainings, the attendance rate was highly successful. What is more several participants are interested also in other modules.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

[SAV - Aktuality - Ponuka tréningov v SAV](#)

[Ponuka tréningov v oblasti rodovej rovnosti - Mladí vedci SAV](#)

[Ústav výskumu sociálnej komunikácie SAV, verejná výskumná inštitúcia - príspevky |](#)

[Facebook](#)

[Ústav výskumu sociálnej komunikácie SAV, verejná výskumná inštitúcia - príspevky |](#)

[Facebook](#)

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Module 2: Gender in research

General information

Venue	Zoom
Date	23 May 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Michaela Jankovičová
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	RISOTO, subcontracted by UVSK SAV
Total number of participants	18
Number of high and middle managers participants	3
Number of HR professionals participants	NA
Number of professors and researchers participants	6
Number of administrative professionals participants	3
Number of students participants	6
Total duration of the module (hours)	3
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Zoom webinar with discussion

Agenda

2 hours: Lecture with videos and examples

1 hour: Discussion, Q&A

Trainer: Michaela Jankovičová (external gender experts)

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

Module 2: Gender in Research (not only in Horizon Europe)

- 1.) What is gender. Gender inequalities
- 2.) Gender bias
- 3.) Horizontal and vertical segregation
- 4.) Feminist reflection of science
- 5.) Sex and gender dimension in research
- 6.) Gender Equality Plan and its role in addressing gender inequalities

Target group: researchers and administrative staff

This module aimed to raise awareness on gender inequalities and their implication for research career and research fields. Our gender expert Michaela Jankovičová from RISOTO provided a wide variety of theoretical information on: gender/sex terminology, gender socialization, gender roles, expectations, horizontal and vertical segregation, glass ceiling, glass elevator and gender in institutions and gender blind vs. gender sensitive research. Finally, we discussed possible tools and strategies how to address gender (or intersectionality) perspectives in research.

Tools and techniques

Zoom meeting was held using:

- Presentations with videos
- Discussion format
- Materials on best practice and examples

Participants' feedback

Some participants also attended Module 1 and they criticized that some information doubled during the Module 2. Nevertheless, Module 2 could not be realized without at least some level of understanding of gender inequalities awareness.

Several participants were critical about lack of cited research in presentations. Trainings were designed more in participatory way, which may not meet the expectations of scientific communities.

Successes and difficulties

The first challenge we have faced is the issue of training promotions. There is no internal platform where we can distribute information of training offers. Therefore, we spent hours in individual invitations to higher management and other internal stakeholders, asking to share information on trainings among their employees. We have also published information on SAS website.

Overall, we were excited that in spite of difficulties in recruitment for trainings, the attendance rate was highly successful. What is more several participants are interested also in other modules.

We now understand that scientific communities are very demanding. We also face several challenges regarding gender bias, which created challenging atmosphere during discussions.

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Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was fairly successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

[SAV - Aktuality - Ponuka tréningov v SAV](#)

[Ponuka tréningov v oblasti rodovej rovnosti - Mladí vedci SAV](#)

[Ústav výskumu sociálnej komunikácie SAV, verejná výskumná inštitúcia - príspevky | Facebook](#)

[Ústav výskumu sociálnej komunikácie SAV, verejná výskumná inštitúcia - príspevky | Facebook](#)

Module 2: Gender in research (2)

General information

Venue	Zoom
Date	14 th October 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Michaela Jankovičová
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	RISOTO, subcontracted by UVSK SAV
Total number of participants	13
Number of high and middle managers participants	2
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	5
Number of administrative professionals participants	2
Number of students participants	4
Total duration of the module (hours)	2,5
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Online zoom meeting webinar with discussions

Agenda

2 hours: Lecture with videos and examples

1 hour: Discussion, Q&A

Trainer: Michaela Jankovičová (external gender experts)

This module was first delivered in May and then repeated in October in order to increase the number of participants and being able to achieve the project's target.

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

Module 2: Gender in Research (not only in Horizon Europe)

- 1.) What is gender. Gender inequalities
- 2.) Gender bias
- 3.) Horizontal and vertical segregation
- 4.) Feminist reflection of science
- 5.) Sex and gender dimension in research
- 6.) Gender Equality Plan and its role in addressing gender inequalities

Target group: researchers and administrative staff

This module aimed to raise awareness on gender inequalities and their implication for research career and research fields. Our gender expert Michaela Jankovičová from RISOTO provided a wide variety of theoretical information on: gender/sex terminology, gender socialization, gender roles, expectations, horizontal and vertical segregation, glass ceiling, glass elevator and gender in institutions and gender blind vs. gender sensitive research. Finally, we discussed possible tools and strategies how to address gender (or intersectionality) perspectives in research.

Tools and techniques

Zoom meeting was held using:

- Presentations with videos
- Discussion format
- Materials on best practice and examples

Participants' feedback

Unfortunately, still during the training we faced several stereotypes and misunderstandings on gender in research and gender equality in research. However, we believe the training helped to open up discussion on challenges and possibilities of gender perspectives in research.

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Successes and difficulties

As with other trainings, we have faced difficulties in recruitment of participants. There is no internal platform where we can distribute information of training offers. Information on the training was published on SAS website.

Overall, we were exited that in spite of difficulties in recruitment for trainings, the attendance rate was highly successful.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was fairly successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

[SAV - Aktuality - Ponuka školenia v SAV: Rod vo výskume](#)

**Ponuka školenia
Rod vo výskume**
(nielen v programe Horizont Európa)

14.10.2022
(piatok)
9:30 - 12:00
online

Michaela Jankovičová, RISOTO
rodová expertka a trénerka diverzity a
inklúzie sa dlhodobo odborne zameriava na
otázky súvisiace so ženami vo vede a
výskume a v STEM

- ako rodová (ne)rovnosť ovplyvňuje vedu
- dôležitosť reflexie rodového hľadiska v každej fáze projektu
- čo znamená integrácia rodu v rámci programu Horizont Európa

RISOTO

ÚSTAV VÝSKUMU
SOCIÁLNEJ
KOMUNIKÁCIE SAV, v.v.i.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416

Module 3: Gender sensitive management

General information

Venue	Zoom, Dúbravská cesta 9, Bratislava (hybrid meeting)
Date	26 th of October 2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Oľga Pietruchová, Gabriel Bianchi, Robert Karul
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	RISOTO, subcontracted by UVSK SAV
Total number of participants	16
Number of high and middle managers participants	11
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	2
Number of administrative professionals participants	3
Number of students participants	0
Total duration of the module (hours)	3
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Hybrid meeting – offline facilitated discussion with streaming and possibility of interaction online

Agenda

2 hours: Lecture with examples on best practice and GE policy, Evaluating the first year of implementation.

1 hour: Discussion, Q&A

Trainers: Oľga Pietruchová (external gender experts) – main lecture, Gabriel Bianchi (GEPI), Róbert Karul (GEPI)

Event pictures

Methodology and content

This training for the management was planned to be mostly a facilitated discussion. Firstly, the gender expert Oľga Pietruchova delivered a short presentation of key goals, principles and examples regarding gender equality. Afterwards, Gabriel Bianchi highlighted the key role of the management of the SAS institutes in the GEP implementation and Róber Karul (GEPI member) presented activities which were already implemented or will be implemented in a short time. The floor was given also to one of the

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directors of the Institute, who presented some of the tools to promote gender equality which the institute has already implemented.

After open discussion with the directors and their chosen representatives, we had a discussion on the evaluation of the first year of GEP implementation and regarding the next steps.

Tools and techniques

The training was built on some theoretical information from the gender expert, completed with the evaluation of existing GEP activities and practical examples of the GEP implementation. The main goal was to increase engagement of management.

Power point presentation, real life experience and case studies to argue were used to promote discussion and engagement of the participants.

Participants' feedback

Participants who attended the meeting welcomed the option to discuss the issue with gender expert, ATHENA and GEPI member as well as with other director of the Institutes. They were discussing the existing goals and activities in the GEP and they wanted to learn more about the role of the management in the process of promoting gender equality within the workspace.

However, they were disappointed that most of the directors did not manage to attend the training. We were struggling for months to reach greater attention from the directors of the Institutes for several reasons: economic situation, accreditation and evaluation period, war in Ukraine and other difficulties related to recent Institutes' transformation have been causing increased stress and time constrains, which ends up by decreasing interest in strategic issues, e.g. gender equality.

Successes and difficulties

We have tried to organize this training from the Spring, and we have faced several challenges regarding organizing. Firstly, we wanted to include the gender training in the existing trainings for the management. But after the February and War in Ukraine, it was suggested to us that trainings are on hold and planned training integration will not be possible. Then, we wanted to organize the training with the cooperation with the SAS Presidium or official Board of directors. Based on previous experience with previous Modules, open call for training may not always be efficient way how to motivate employees to participate. Therefore, we wanted to organize the event with a partner which would bring a greater importance and status to the training. But this cooperation took some time and mostly, it was again suggested not to organize trainings in the summer. On the other hand, the date in Autumn was again problematic regarding the date, place and other planned events for the management. Even though we set the date and organize the training in the cooperation, the overall attendance was very low.

On the other hand, as a response to this event, we were already asked to repeat or prepare similar event for the directors again in January 2023. So although we saw this event as not that successful, it was a "foot in a door", which helped us to start a greater discussion and engagement on the management.

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Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was not too successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

This training was not disseminated on the social media due to the overall low participation.

Module 4: Empowerment

General information

Venue	Dúbravská cesta 9, Bratislava, Slovakia (Slovak Academy of Sciences)
Date	21.9.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Oľga Pietruchová
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	RISOTO
Total number of participants	9
Number of high and middle managers participants	1
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	4
Number of administrative professionals participants	1
Number of students participants	3
Total duration of the module (hours)	3 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Interactive workshop

Agenda

Module 4: Empowerment

- 1.) *What is gender and discrimination, what is inclusion and diversity*
- 2.) *Challenges women face in science*
- 3.) *Horizontal and vertical segregation*
- 4.) *Sexism*
- 5.) *Strategies to empower and argue for gender equality*

Event pictures

Methodology and content

This training module was aimed to be an opportunity not only to improve knowledge about gender equality issues, but also to develop and practice skills to argue for gender equality. Therefore, the lower focus was put on theoretical information and more on discussions and arguing exercises. This training was specifically prepared only for women in our research organizations so we could create a safe space where also negative experience can be share and understood. Using real life experience was an opportunity to show, how gender inequalities affect our lives, what are the strategies to empower ourselves and our research community and how to actually argue for gender equality. The training was built on theoretical information which were combined and used during the practical skills learning exercises.

Tools and techniques

The training was built on theoretical information which were combined and used during the practical skills learning exercises. Power point presentation, real life experience and case studies to argue were used.

Participants' feedback

Participants' feedback was very positive. They appreciated the interactive format of the training and lived experience which can only be experienced during the offline workshops.

Here are some of the comments from participants:

“Although I know a lot about the issue of gender and discrimination it is always difficult for me to discuss it with someone. It was useful to think more about the arguments, opportunities for gender equality.”

“We can see that gender equality is a democratic value. But even if we live in democratic society, we should not expect that it is fully achieved.”

Many participants see a lot of work in front of us in order to achieve gender equality and diversity in teams. It is not only gender, but also age, which matters in scientific fields. Work-life balance was stressed as another important issue.

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Successes and difficulties

However, the training was not delivered without difficulties. It was organized as “open training” in which employees from the Slovak academy of sciences can freely participate. The first date in June had to be cancelled due to the sickness of our gender expert. About 20 participants have signed for the training, but at the end only 8 of them were really able to attend. Some participants were sick, or limited by COVID-19 in family, some decided to give a preference to unexpected working duties. Considering the first interest, the training was organized with great effort, but the finished quantified outputs are limited. But regardless of this, we believe this training had a highest level of potential to create real shift in mindset of our participants.

In future, trainings should be probably organized with cooperation with single institutes in order to achieve at least some level of commitment to really attend the training.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

The image shows two screenshots of Facebook posts. The left post is from 'Ústav výskumu sociálnej komunikácie SAV, verejná výskumná inštitúcia' and the right post is from 'Risoto'. Both posts feature a photograph of a person's hands painted with rainbow colors. The SAV post includes text about the training on diversity and gender equality, mentioning a grant from the European Union. The Risoto post expresses gratitude for the training and mentions the SAV partner.

(1) [Ústav výskumu sociálnej komunikácie SAV, verejná výskumná inštitúcia - príspevky | Facebook](#)

(2) [Risoto - príspevky | Facebook](#)

Module 5: Sexual harassment on workplace

General information

Venue	Slovakia (Slovak Academy of Sciences – Zoom meeting due to COVID restrictions)
Date	18.03.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Doc. Slávka Karkošková
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Inštitút pre výskum práce a rodiny (Institute for Work and Family Research)
Total number of participants	25
Number of high and middle managers participants	23
Number of HR professionals participants	
Number of professors and researchers participants	22
Number of administrative professionals participants	1
Number of students participants	1 (Athena team member)
Total duration of the module (hours)	4 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Online webinar

Agenda

Sexual harassment: definition, Slovak legislation, discrimination at workplace, best-practice, psychological first-aid for the employees who were violated.

Event pictures

Due to the sensitivity of the training's topic, no further pictures were taken. Participants were ambivalent about the possible public promotion of the event. Participants agreed on the picture for the purpose of an attendance list.

Methodology and content

Training was organized by one of our GEPI committee member Dr. Robert Karul (also a head of the Committee for Equal Opportunities at SAS) who invited an expert on sexual harassment and gender-based violence. So, this training was not held by the gender expert subcontracted through the ATHENA project, but the activity and the training is the

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initiative of ATHENA project and GEP implementation. Directors, middle-management and representatives from the trade unions were invited to the training.

The trainings addressed several issues: *Sexual harassment: definition, Slovak legislation, discrimination at workplace, best-practice, psychological first-aid for the employees who were violated.*

Tools and techniques

Zoom meeting was held using:

- Presentation
- Discussion format
- Study materials on best practice

Participants' feedback

Great concerns on boundaries in behaviour were raised: participants were curious about the proper signs of a harassment. That pointed to the greater need to address raising awareness on gender equality issue in general. Some level of gender bias appeared during the discussions. On the other hand, directors showed that it is important to them to prevent any form of sexual harassment and address and intervene as soon as possible.

To sum up, it was visible it is an extremely sensitive topic. No director and nor workplace are willing to admit this problem can be present, although they are willing to learn more and be active agents in prevention and measures against sexual harassment or gender-based violence.

It was pointed out that SAS is currently missing the transparent policy and recommendations which would address the sexual harassment prevention. The head of the Committee for Equal opportunities at SAS (also member of GEPI committee) informed about the plan of adopting such policy.

Successes and difficulties

It was the first training motivated by the adopted GEP. The issue of sexual harassment is very sensitive and clearly, managements of the organization within the SAS would prefer if this did not have to be addressed. Even the attendance list had to be taken with greater sensitivity. The training on sexual harassment is still perceived as something which should be hidden, not publicly shared. It is against the expressed interest of the attendees, as they want to achieve respectful and safe environment. It shows that sexual harassment in our cultural context is still a taboo, which needs to be carefully addressed.

Despite of this, the number of participants who attended this first training is really satisfactory.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

This training has not been publicly disseminated due to the sensitivity of the issue.

Module 5: Sexual harassment on workplace (2)

General information

Venue	Dúbravská cesta 9, Bratislava, Slovakia (Slovak Academy of Sciences) + online through Zoom (hybrid meeting)
Date	19.9.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Oľga Pietruchová
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	RISOTO
Total number of participants	15
Number of high and middle managers participants	3
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	5
Number of administrative professionals participants	2
Number of students participants	5
Total duration of the module (hours)	2 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Hybrid event with presentation and discussions

Agenda

Sexual harassment: definition, Slovak legislation, discrimination at workplace, best-practice

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

Training was initiated by the director of our institute, as she has previously attended the training for directors on 18th of March 2022. Through the training she wanted to open the discussion on sexual harassment issue as well as to set the clear policy of our institute. Therefore, the training was similar with the content of the Module 5 delivered in March, but it was not focused exclusively on higher management. Here, the aim was to open the sensitive issue in a relatively small team. Therefore, we invited the ATHENA gender expert from the RISOTO team, Olga Pietruchova to tell us more about the definitions of sexual harassment and overlapping themes such as fair working conditions, discrimination, diversity. Olga Pietruchova, former director of the public Department of gender equality in Slovakia also provided us with the history of policies in Slovakia together with the international context.

The presentation was followed by the discussion on different cases and optimal scenario how to approach sexual harassment within research organizations.

The trainings addressed several issues: *Sexual harassment: definition, Slovak legislation, discrimination at workplace, best-practice and case studies.*

Tools and techniques

Power point presentation was used to provide the participants with basic information of the topic. Lecture was present with most of the participants "offline", some participants due to the quarantine or work trip have joined us online.

After the presentation we had an open discussion facilitated by the gender expert.

Participants' feedback

The topics was perceived with acceptance and interest by participants. We identified several challenges regarding the topics:

- The absence of clear policy on sexual harassment (such policy is now being prepared, but the individual institutes must accept their own policies)
- We discussed how to address the issue in small teams, where working relationships are close, single person can have several positions and power is often centralized. Even though it is not a problem now, we agreed on the need to apply some preventive mechanisms for future.

Successes and difficulties

This training was delivered thanks to the special interest and attitude of our director. Although other directors at the Slovak Academy of Sciences have attended the training in March, none of them were so far interested to deliver the issue in their institutes. The taboo and stigma of this topics is very strong, and it is changing slowly.

We plan to ask directors in autumn to again consider delivering trainings with cooperation with our gender expert and we will see what will be the response.

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Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

[\(2\) Ústav výskumu sociálnej komunikácie SAV, verejná výskumná inštitúcia - príspevky | Facebook](#)

[\(1\) Risoto - príspevky | Facebook](#)

Module 6: Gender sensitive language

General information

Venue	Slovakia (Slovak Academy of Sciences – Webex meeting due to COVID restrictions)
Date	28.04.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Jana Cviková (GEPI member) Lucia Molnár Satinská (researcher of the SAS) Róbert Karul (GEPI, Commission for the Equal Opportunities at the SAS)
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Jana Cviková (GEPI member) - Institute of World Literature SAS & NGO Aspekt Lucia Molnár Satinská (researcher of the SAS) - Ľ. Štúr Institute of Linguistics SAS Róbert Karul (GEPI, Commission for the Equal Opportunities at the SAS, Institute of Philosophy)
Total number of participants	15
Number of high and middle managers participants	3 (+1 GEPI member who is also a member of the SAS Presidium)
Number of HR professionals participants	NA
Number of professors and researchers participants	8
Number of administrative professionals participants	2
Number of students participants	2
Total duration of the module (hours)	3 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Online workshop

Agenda

Feminist perspectives on language
Slovak language and its possibilities to use inclusive language.
Examples and dilemmas
Gender Equality Plan of the SAS – discussing how language was applied.
Discussion

Event pictures

Methodology and content

This training has a workshop format. Therefore, the main lectures only proposed some theoretical background on feminism and language and afterwards there was a wide discussion on dilemmas, challenges which we face when deciding to use gender sensitive or gender inclusive language.

Workshop was closed to the invited participants from the SAS – mostly researcher on language and literature, representatives from the GEPI and other committees and members from the SAS Presidency.

In Slovak language, generic masculinism is widely used. But there are some first attempts to make women in language more visible. However, this may bring several challenges from extending the texts, difficulties in readability or even political gender back-lash.

Considering the specific challenges of Slovak language, we have identified several conclusions:

- We understand the role of language in forming attitudes.
- Text should be evaluated as a whole.
- We cannot bring universal recommendation, but the text should show the signal of gender inclusivity. There are several strategies which can be creatively applied, with considering the readability and style of the texts.

One of the follow up of the training will be creating a manual from recommendations and examples, how the SAS institutions can apply gender inclusive language.

Tools and techniques

Zoom meeting was held using:

- Presentations
- Discussion format
- Materials on best practice and examples
- Call for cooperation – there is an ambition to create a working document on recommendation how to use gender sensitive language within institutions

Participants' feedback

The issue was welcomed by participants. Several brought comments how challenging is to reflect gender equality in Slovak language. We have discussed also political implications and practical challenges regarding the length of the text and its readability.

Good examples from the presenters delivered overall understanding that there is no unified way how to use gender sensitive language.

The need for the working documents which would address the main challenges and possible solutions when preparing the texts is more than welcome and it will be prepared by experts.

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Successes and difficulties

Although the training was not aimed to invite all employees from the SAS, we expected that more members from the existing committees and from the management will attend the meeting. The problem of absenting the gender sensitive language can be solved only in discussion. Overall, although we have expected more participants, we believe there was a useful discussion and probably this event will not be the last one.

Also, trainings were offered in hybrid format, allowing to choose whether participants prefer to attend offline/online. We see there is a tendency to prefer online formats. This will be reflected also in future trainings.

Last, but not least, it was mentioned several times during the training, that we face severe gender backlash and also, regarding the war in Ukraine, cuts in funding within the institution, people are articulating doubts whether gender equality is a priority to deal with right now. Nevertheless, we hope these tendencies will not negatively affect the trainings.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

Invitation for the training were disseminated though email. We are attaching the invite leaflet. We have reported the training on facebook page: [Ústav výskumu sociálnej komunikácie SAV, verejná výskumná inštitúcia - príspevky | Facebook](#)

Seminár o rodovo inkluzívnom používaní jazyka (nielen) v SAV

Pozývame Vás na seminár, ktorého cieľom je predstaviť teoretické aj praktické východiská používania rodovo inkluzívneho jazyka a hľadať i ponúknuť riešenia konkrétnych jazykových problémov s tým spojených.

Seminár pripravujú:

PhDr. Jana Cviková, PhD. (Ústav svetovej literatúry SAV, v. v. i.) a PhDr. Lucia Molnár Satinská, PhD. (Jazykovedný ústav Ľudovíta Štúra SAV, v. v. i.),
Komisia SAV pre rovnosť príležitostí a ATHENA

Termín 28. apríl 9:30 - 12:30

(hybridný formát: online a prezenčne na Úrade SAV)

3.6 URAK training programme

Training Topic: *Sustainable equality of women and men in the science*

Module 1: Unconscious bias and gender-based violence

General information

Venue	University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev", Kaneff Center
Date	28.10.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Tanya Grozeva, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Daniel Pavlov
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev"
Total number of participants	14
Number of high and middle managers participants	12
Number of HR professionals participants	-
Number of professors and researchers participants	-
Number of administrative professionals participants	-
Number of students participants	2
Total duration of the module (hours)	2
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Classroom lesson

Agenda

14:00 – 14:05 Official opening.

14:05 – 14:15 Presentation of project ATHENA.

14:15 – 15:00 Module 1. Introduction to "Unconscious bias"

15:00 – 15:45 Module 2. Role of GEP at URAK to avoid unconscious bias, gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

15:45 – 16:00 Discussion and official closure.

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

Module 1: Introduction to “Unconscious bias”.

1.1 Understanding of “unconscious bias”.

1.2 Understanding of “gender-based violence, including sexual harassment”.

Module 2: Role of GEP at URAK to avoid unconscious bias, gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

2.1 Good practices at employment process.

2.2 Good practices at attestation process.

Tools and techniques

It was used a classic interactive lecture.

The main materials have been presented by a power point presentation and then the lecturer (the expert delivering the training) initiated active discussion on each module. Thus the participants have been actively involved in the training by encouraging them to comment how the GEP at URAK will keep the already existing high level of tolerance women-men at the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev” under this specific Topic 1.

Participants’ feedback

The participants liked mostly the idea that the GEP will keep the already existing high level of tolerance women-men at the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev” under this specific Topic 1. They confirm that the approved regulations (done during the training) eliminate environment for unconscious bias and gender-based violence.

Successes and difficulties

The event was very successful, because all participants have a high understanding that the equal opportunities for females and males in the academia world are fundamental.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Module 2: Work-life balance and organizational culture

General information

Venue	University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev", Kaneff Center
Date	25.10.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Tanya Grozeva, Prof. DSc Diana Antonova, Academic DSc Hristo Beloev
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev"
Total number of participants	27
Number of high and middle managers participants	27
Number of HR professionals participants	-
Number of professors and researchers participants	-
Number of administrative professionals participants	-
Number of students participants	-
Total duration of the module (hours)	2
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Classroom lesson

Agenda

14:00 – 14:05 Official opening.

14:05 – 14:15 Presentation of project ATHENA.

14:15 – 15:00 Module 1. Understanding of "Work-life balance and organizational culture".

15:00 – 15:45 Module 2. Ensuring equal opportunities for women and men in the process of studying students and doctoral students, in obtaining scientific degrees, in occupying academic positions and positions in the University administration.

15:45 – 16:00 Discussion and official closure.

Event pictures

Methodology and content

Module 1: Understanding of “Work-life balance and organizational culture”.

- 1.1 Introduction to the “work-life-balance”.
- 1.2 Main requirements to the organizational culture.

Module 2: Ensuring equal opportunities for women and men in the process of studying students and doctoral students, in obtaining scientific degrees, in occupying academic positions and positions in the University administration.

- 2.1 Main internal documents at URAK.
- 2.2 The role of GEP for the work-life balance and organizational culture at URAK.

Tools and techniques

This training was done during the meeting of the Academic Council of the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev”. In fact, the main lecturers Assoc. Prof. Dr. Tanya Grozeva and Prof. DSc. Diana Antonova explained why URAK should make some of the changes in our internal regulations. The last of the four pictures is the moment when our Rector Academic DSc Hristo Beloev asked the members of the Academic Council to approve the given propositions. The pictures show that all members of the Academic Council support the proposed changes!

Participants’ feedback

The participants support the GEP at the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev” under this specific Topic 2. Their vote confirms the sustainability of the mentality in our university, based on equal academic opportunities for women and men.

Successes and difficulties

The event was very successful, because all participants confirmed with their vote the equal opportunities for females and males. The combination of a training during a session of the Academic council is well-done initiative because such training creates equal understanding of this issue (work-life balance and organizational culture) among all the representatives of the high management level.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Module 3: Gender equality in leadership positions and decision-making

General information

Venue	University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev", PhD central room
Date	14.11.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Galina Ivanova, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Daniel Pavlov
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev"
Total number of participants	17
Number of high and middle managers participants	-
Number of HR professionals participants	-
Number of professors and researchers participants	17
Number of administrative professionals participants	-
Number of students participants	-
Total duration of the module (hours)	2
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Classroom lesson

Agenda

- 16:00 – 16:05 Official opening.
- 16:05 – 16:15 Presentation of project ATHENA.
- 16:15 – 17:00 Module 1.
- 17:00 – 17:45 Module 2.
- 17:45 – 18:00 Discussion and official closure.

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

Module 1: Ensuring the equal opportunities of women and men to be involved in decision-making jobs in the University.

1.1 Introduction to the national legal frame.

1.2 Introduction to the election procedures of URAK

Module 2: Ensuring equal payments of women and men on decision-making jobs.

2.1 Main internal documents at URAK for different payments.

2.2 The role of GEP for development of sustainable legislation in URAK about this topic.

Tools and techniques

It was used a classic interactive lecture.

The two lecturers used Power point slides to present ATHENA project and the efforts of the international project team to create environment for sustainable equal opportunities between women and men in the science, thanks to GEP.

The discussion with the audience has raised some comments which indicated that the audience has rather highlevel of tolerance women-men at the University of Ruse “

Participants' feedback

The participants listened rather carefully the lecture. Then their comments confirmed that the national mentality of the people, who are employed in the educational sector, is tolerant and supportive about equal opportunities of the women-men to take leadership positions and decision-making process.

Successes and difficulties

The event was very successful, because all participants confirmed that there are no restrictions for women and men for equality in leadership positions and decision-making process.

Two of the PhD students at URAK are also important political members of the Municipality Council of our city (Mrs Nora Stoyanova and Mr Trayan Totev). Both of them have given quite positive feedback about the efforts of ATHENA team to keep the equality between females and males in the science on the base of GEP!

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Module 4: Gender equality in career progression and recruitment

General information

Venue	University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev", Rectorat
Date	22.11.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Vanya Panteleeva, Assoc. Prof. Dr. Daniel Pavlov
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev"
Total number of participants	9
Number of high and middle managers participants	-
Number of HR professionals participants	-
Number of professors and researchers participants	-
Number of administrative professionals participants	-
Number of students participants	9
Total duration of the module (hours)	2
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Classroom lesson

Agenda

- 17:00 – 17:05 Official opening.
- 17:05 – 17:15 Presentation of project ATHENA.
- 17:15 – 18:00 Module 1.
- 18:00 – 18:45 Module 2.
- 18:45 – 19:00 Discussion and official closure.

Event pictures

Methodology and content

Module 1: Ensuring the equal opportunities of women and men to be recruited at the University.

1.1 Introduction to the national legal frame.

1.2 Introduction to the internal procedures of URAK

Module 2: Ensuring the career progression of women and men at the University.

2.1 Main internal documents at URAK.

2.2 The role of GEP for development of sustainable legislation in URAK about this topic.

Tools and techniques

It was used a classic interactive lecture.

The main focus was to discuss how the GEP supports the gender equality in career progression and recruitment at the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev”.

Participants’ feedback

The participants liked mostly the idea that the GEP will keep the already existing gender equality in career progression and recruitment. The discussion of the legal frame has shown how the students could foresee their academic career at the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev” in case they prefer to become scientists.

Successes and difficulties

The event was very successful, because all participants have a high understanding how the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev” provides gender equality in career progression and recruitment. These comments have been shared both by female and male participants.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Module 5: Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content its effects in the work environment

General information

Venue	University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev", Rectorat
Date	29.11.2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Assoc. Prof. Dr. Tanya Grozeva, Prof. DSc. Diana Antonova
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of Ruse "Angel Kanchev"
Total number of participants	175
Number of high and middle managers participants	41
Number of HR professionals participants	2
Number of professors and researchers participants	
Number of administrative professionals participants	111
Number of students participants	21
Total duration of the module (hours)	2
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Classroom lesson

Agenda

- 14:00 – 14:05 Official opening.
- 14:05 – 14:15 Presentation of project ATHENA.
- 14:15 – 15:00 Module 1.
- 15:00 – 15:45 Module 2.
- 15:45 – 16:00 Discussion and official closure.

Event pictures

Methodology and content

Module 1: Ensuring the equal opportunities of women and men to provide research and teaching at the University.

1.1 Prevention against violence, as violation of human rights and form of discrimination gender based.

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1.2 Introduction to the internal procedures of URAK.

Module 2: The role of GEP on the equal opportunities of women and men to provide research and teaching at the University

2.1 Main actions in GEP of URAK.

2.2 Expected outcomes from GEP.

Tools and techniques

This training was done during the meeting of the General Assembly of the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev”. The main lecturers Assoc. Prof. Dr. Tanya Grozeva and Prof. DSc. Diana Antonova explained why URAK should make some of the changes in our internal regulations. The second picture is from the moment when the members of the General Assembly voted to approve the suggested propositions.

Participants’ feedback

The integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content is recognised as fundamental for the successful development of the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev”. The female participants of the General Assembly who didn’t approve some of the proposed changes in the internal regulations were afraid that the fact of discussing this discrimination is a precondition to create discrimination.

Successes and difficulties

The event was very successful, because all participants have a high understanding that the GEP makes stronger the equal opportunities for females and males in the academia world. The female participants of the General Assembly who didn’t approve some of the proposed changes in the internal regulations were afraid that the fact of discussing this discrimination is a precondition to create discrimination.

The proposed changes in the internal regulation have been positively discussed by the Academic Council on 25.10.2022 and now (29.11.2022) they were approved by the General Assembly of the university, too.

Important moment - the main ATHENA texts, which were approved during the General Assembly of the University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev” have been previously prepared with great contribution of Prof. Dr. Sasho Penov while he had been the external expert of URAK under ATHENA for the WP3 and WP4 (November 2021 - May 2022). At the time of this voting (29.11.2022) Prof. Dr. Sasho Penov is already the Minister of Education of Bulgaria!

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

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3.7 FRCT training programme

Training Topic: *Gender equality at FRCT*

Module 1: Unconscious bias

General information

Venue	FRCT
Date	19/09/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Anna Christina da Silva
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of the Azores
Total number of participants	11
Number of high and middle managers participants	2
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	0
Number of administrative professionals participants	9
Number of students participants	0
Total duration of the module (hours)	3 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	classroom lesson

Agenda

14:00 – 17:00 AZOT: Unconscious Bias

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Methodology and content

- Understand “the nature of unconscious bias and how it may affect our judgment and decision-making” (Gender training programme. Guidelines).
- Explore the «categories of perception» theorized by the French philosopher and sociologist Pierre Bourdieu in his book *Masculine Domination*.
- Sensitize the participants to a consequent reflection on the principles of submission and domination in their historical, cultural and philosophical bias.
- The training was organised in two registers: theoretical, exposure of content, concepts, arguments, and theories; theoretical and practical, questioning, analysis, exploration of texts and their nuclear content, as well as practical exercises to consolidate learning.
- The methodology was interactive, centered on the trainees, favouring the development of skills in consulting relevant documentation, production of reasoned argumentation, debate of ideas in small and large groups, favouring the construction of explanatory schemes of the issues addressed.

Tools and techniques

- PowerPoint presentations
- Infographics
- Videos
- Texts

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Participants' feedback

The participants showed interest in the reflections that were proposed and were confronted with the need to think against themselves and deconstruct inherited paradigms without critical reflection.

Successes and difficulties

Provide participants with a weekly workload so that they can read excerpts from the books that appear in the bibliographic reference of the training action. The previous reading of some texts helps in the reflection and understanding of the theme of the training action.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/frctazores_igualdaddegenero-activity-6977669831722438656-DbdH?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop
- <https://twitter.com/FRCTAzores/status/1571904428524830724?t=jv622cX6qhNpTzlj8roiNQ&s=19>

Module 2: The gender dimension in research

General information

Venue	FRCT
Date	20/10/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Berta Maria Oliveira Pimentel
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of the Azores
Total number of participants	9
Number of high and middle managers participants	2
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	0
Number of administrative professionals participants	7
Number of students participants	0
Total duration of the module (hours)	3
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Classroom lesson

Agenda

14:00-17:00 **AZOT**: Gender Dimension in Research

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

The methodology was interactive and focused on the trainees, encouraging the development of skills in consulting relevant documentation, producing reasoned argumentation, and debating ideas in small and large groups, to build explanatory schemes for the issues addressed.

The main topics of the module were:

- Reasons for the gender dimension in research;
- The traditional view associating science with men and the scope of women's visibility in research and scientific innovation. Examples of good practices;
- Gender dimension in research as a scientific topic itself;
- United Nations and European Union (EU) key documents about gender dimension in research;
- EU guidelines for gender mainstreaming in research;
- The case of Portugal / gender dimension in research in Portugal.

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Tools and techniques

The training was organized in two registers: theoretical, exposure of content, concepts, arguments, and theories; theoretical and practical, questioning, analysis, and exploration of texts and their nuclear content, as well as practical exercises, to consolidate learning. Different materials were used such as PowerPoint presentations with infographics, videos and texts.

Participants' feedback

In general, the training participants demonstrated an interest in the theme as well as a critical spirit when confronted with some of the ideas and aporias presented, actively participating in the dialogues held during this training. Their involvement and sharing of experiences enhanced the session.

Successes and difficulties

The trainees' sensitivity concerning the themes of the gender dimension in research made the training the most simple. The difficulties presented are related to the fact that there is still a lack of awareness about some aspects of the gender inequality phenomenon. These difficulties, however, are being overcome by events of this nature.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

The training was not disseminated via FRCT social media channels.

Module 3: Work-life balance and organisational culture

General information

Venue	FRCT
Date	03/10/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Maria Cecília de Miranda Nogueira Coelho
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais- UFMG - Brasil
Total number of participants	11
Number of high and middle managers participants	1
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	0
Number of administrative professionals participants	10
Number of students participants	0
Total duration of the module (hours)	3 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Lesson

Agenda

14:00-17:00 **AZOT**: Work-life balance and organisational culture

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

The theoretical texts that supported and/or inspired the presentation were:

1) PARKER, Rozsika *The Subversive Stitch: Embroidery and the Making of the Feminine*. London: Bloomsbury Visual Arts, 2019 (1984*).

Through reports, letters, women's magazines, novels, the author (1945-2010) analyses the difference between female embroidery work, considered a craft, and male painting work, marginalized throughout history. From Penelope to women weavers and embroiderers until the mid-twentieth century, women's position is that of domestic work, supported by a husband, which in the images analysed throughout history (American, mainly) they expect. Embroidery is linked to modesty, silence and female submission. Beautifully illustrated, her book also discusses the contradictory nature of women's experience of embroidery: how it has inculcated female subservience while providing an immensely pleasurable source of creativity, forging links between women.

2) DARDOT, Liliane; ALMADA, Márcia, *The heart of the place: testimonials for Guimarães Rosa*, Cordisburgo. Belo Horizonte: SEC, 2006.

The book proposes a dialogue between individual and collective memories of residents of the city where one of the most important Brazilian writers, Guimarães Rosa, was born. In connection with the writer's letters, archived in the city's museum, is the interpretation of the (more prosaic) themes alluded there by elderly women, from the Estrelas do Sertão group. In contrast to the written word, manual work, embroidery and sewing are done that reveal the vision of these women regarding the themes addressed in the letters by the writer. This project, which gives visibility and voice to women, meets another project, the embroiderers and weavers of Vale do Jequitinhonha, in Minas Gerais, in which women achieved their financial autonomy through manual work and also the electronic registration of verses that they sing during this work, and that were adapted to serve an external audience, because during the pandemic, they sold adapted verses for each customer who ordered a song for himself by phone.

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3) CUNHA, Mário V., *Handkerchiefs of boyfriends - writings of love*. Vila Verde: Artisan Alliance, 2002.

In this record of scarves, posters and anonymous, made in Portugal since the 17th century, we see the use of the scarf as a feminine mark for the loved one to remember the loved one and keep the commitment, even being in distant lands. The embroidered lines indicate the women's dependence and their attitude of waiting for the lover's return. The theme dialogues with the use of the scarf in poems, plays and cinema, as in Shakespeare's *Othello* and *Agora*, by Amenábar (about the legendary scarf scene by Hypatia), showing the weight of the symbolic load of this small object.

Reflect on the historical character of Hypatia de Alexandria who is considered the first female scientist in the history of Western culture.

To problematize the representations of Hypatia de Alexandria in the 21st century focusing on the gender stereotypes that mark the daily life of women scientists.

Tools and techniques

- PowerPoint presentations
- Infographics
- Videos
- Texts

Participants' feedback

The participants showed interest in the reflections that were proposed. They were confronted with the need to think against themselves and deconstruct inherited paradigms without critical reflection.

Successes and difficulties

Provide participants with a weekly workload so that they can read excerpts from the books that appear in the bibliographic reference of the training action. I think that the previous reading of some texts helps in the reflection and understanding of the theme of the training action.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was very successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

The content of the training action was recorded in digital video format.

Module 4: How to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment

General information

Venue	FRCT
Date	10/10/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Paulo Vitorino Fontes
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of the Azores
Total number of participants	11
Number of high and middle managers participants	3
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	0
Number of administrative professionals participants	8
Number of students participants	0
Total duration of the module (hours)	3 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Classroom lesson

Agenda

14:00-17:00 AZOT: How to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

The methodology was interactive and centred on the trainees, encouraging the development of skills in consulting pertinent documentation, producing reasoned argumentation, and debating ideas in small and large groups to construct explanatory schemes for the addressed issues.

The following information was covered in module 4 “How to combat gender-based violence and sexual harassment”:

- 1.) Gender bias and concepts of gender-based violence and sexual harassment in institutional cultures;
- 2.) Policies to fight gender-based violence;
- 3.) Practices to improve policies to fight against sexual harassment at work, with a focus on RPOs/RFOs.

Tools and techniques

- PowerPoint presentations
- Infographics
- Videos
- Texts

Participants' feedback

In general, the training participants demonstrated an interest in the theme as well as a critical spirit when confronted with some of the ideas and aporias presented, actively participating in the dialogues held during this training.

Successes and difficulties

The trainees' sensitivity to the topics of non-domestic violence and gender equality made the training the most straightforward. A lack of sensitivity and awareness regarding certain aspects of the phenomenon of gender inequality also contributes to the obstacles. However, these challenges are being overcome by events of this nature. Future events should invite trainers not only from the academy but also from social organizations that deal with these issues to increase the diversity of training experiences.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was fairly successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

The content of the training action was recorded in digital video format.

Module 5: Tools for an inclusive language its effects in the work environment

General information

Venue	FRCT
Date	17/10/2022
Full name of the expert delivering the training	Paulo Vitorino Fontes
Name of the organization to which the expert belongs	University of the Azores
Total number of participants	9
Number of high and middle managers participants	1
Number of HR professionals participants	0
Number of professors and researchers participants	0
Number of administrative professionals participants	8
Number of students participants	0
Total duration of the module (hours)	3 hours
Format (classroom lesson, webinar, etc.)	Classroom lesson

Agenda

14:00-17:00 AZOT: Tools for an inclusive language

Event pictures

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Methodology and content

The methodology was interactive and focused on the trainees, encouraging the development of skills in consulting relevant documentation, producing reasoned argumentation, and debating ideas in small and large groups, to build explanatory schemes for the issues addressed.

Tools for an inclusive language:

- 1.) National and international legal-political instruments on gender equality.
- 2.) Language, symbolic representations and power.
- 3.) Tools for the application of inclusive language.

Tools and techniques

The training was organized in two registers: theoretical, exposure of content, concepts, arguments, and theories; theoretical and practical, questioning, analysis, and exploration of texts and their nuclear content, as well as practical exercises, to consolidate learning. Different materials were used such as PowerPoint presentations with infographics, videos and texts.

Participants' feedback

In general, the training participants demonstrated an interest in the theme as well as a critical spirit when confronted with some of the ideas and aporias presented, actively participating in the dialogues held during this training. Their involvement and sharing of experiences enhanced the session.

Successes and difficulties

The trainees' sensitivity concerning the themes of inclusive language or non-sexist language made the training the most simple. The difficulties are related to the fact that there is still a lack of sensitivity and awareness about some aspects of the gender inequality phenomenon. These difficulties, however, are being overcome by events of this nature.

Event assessment

The partner reports that overall the event was fairly successful.

Links for the dissemination of the training

The content of the training action was recorded in digital video format.

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4. Material of the Gender Training Programme

The material used by each ATHENA institution in their institutional gender trainings may be consulted at the project e-platform (www.gender-equality.eu). It has been created a dedicated site to share it publicly so it can be accessible to any other organization interested in implementing institutional gender trainings.

The material can be directly assessed by the following link: <https://gender-equality.eu/materials/>

Figure 1. How to access the material at the ATHENA e-platform shows a screenshot on how to access the training material through the project e-platform. Any interested person should follow the following steps:

1. Access the project e-platform via www.gender-equality.eu
2. Click on the 'Trainings' item at the menu bar on the top.
3. Once inside the 'Trainings' site, click on 'Resources for institutional gender trainings' that can be found under the main page slogan.

Figure 1. How to access the material at the ATHENA e-platform

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5. ATHENA 2nd Mutual Learning Workshop (MLW)

5.1 Objectives of the Mutual Learning Workshop

The 2nd Mutual Learning Workshop (MLW), whose topic was '*Shared experiences on the process of implementing the Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and the organisation of events and trainings*', was intended to GEPI Committee members and project partners and reinforced the objective of **sharing and commonly learning** from the experiences of each ATHENA institution in the process of implementing their tailored Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). From this common exercise, the following outcomes were expected:

- Learning from main challenges and ways of overcoming them.
- Key aspects to consider for the next steps of the GEPs implementation, monitoring and assessment.
- Lessons learnt to be considered for the organisation of future events.

The ATHENA institutions that developed their GEPs were invited to make a 15-min. presentation commenting on how the GEP was implemented; the current status of their GEP; main barriers/challenges encountered; how the monitoring and evaluation of the GEP will be undertaken; and how the GEP has been and will be disseminated within the institution and externally.

On the other hand, project partners were also invited to share the main challenges/barriers and the lessons learned derived from the events and trainings organised under the ATHENA framework.

5.2 'Shared experiences on the process of implementing the Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and the organisation of events and trainings': The event.

The 2nd project MLW was carried out on 17 January 2023 in a hybrid format. The event was organised by Consulta Europa, partner responsible for this task, with the support of JSI project partners, who hosted the event at the [Jožef Stefan Institute](#) in Ljubljana, Slovenia. The organisation and planning of the MLW included the following elements: strategic planning, agenda development, invitation management and registrations as well as monitoring and evaluation. Project partners and GEPI Committee members were officially invited, and a Zoom link was facilitated for those participants who could not attend in person. A total of 44 participants attended the event: 27 in person and 17 online.

The event agenda may be consulted in the Annex. Prof. Boštjan Zalar, director of the Jožef Stefan Institute, opened the event and welcomed participants. Then, Marlene Santacruz, member of the project coordination team at Consulta Europa, presented the project progress. After this introduction, each project institution that has developed

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its GEP intervened in a 15-min presentation sharing how its institutional process of GEP implementation was undertaken.

Finally, there was a workshop on *Good Practices in the Implementation of GEPs* facilitated by Gabriela Langhammerová, an external expert on Gender Equality Plans at the Centre for Gender and Science (NKC). This workshop was followed by a discussion group where partners took the opportunity to learn from external feedback and then the conclusions of the workshop were shared.

Figure 2, 2, 3 and 4 below show various photos taken during the event at different stages, such as the opening speech from Prof. Boštjan Zalar, some project partners presentations and the Workshop on Good Practices.

Figure 2. Prof. Boštjan Zalar, director of the Jožef Stefan Institute, opening speech

Figure 2. UJK's presentation

Figure 3. FRCT's presentation

Figure 4. Workshop on Good Practices in the Implementation of GEPs

The event recording is publicly available at the project YouTube channel [here](#).

5.3 Event figures

As abovementioned, 44 participants registered to the event. As it can be seen in Figure 5, most of the participants to the MLW were female (79%), with an attendance of 21% of male participants. The low percentage of men allyship is an issue that has also been previously identified in other project events. Future project events should direct efforts at engaging more men in support of gender equality, diversity and inclusion.

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Figure 5. Gender balance of participants.

Figure 6 displays the number of participants by project organisation. As it can be seen, the whole consortium was represented in the event.

Figure 6. Number of participants per ATHENA institutions at the Mutual Learning Workshop

5.4 Event conclusions and evaluation

The MLW was an opportunity for mutual sharing and learning about the process undertaken by each ATHENA RPO/RFO to implement the tailored GEPs. Project partners could also discuss the main challenges faced in relation to the events and trainings organised under the project's framework. The consortium considered the event very satisfactory and both the workshop on Good Practices and the subsequent joint discussion were very enriching.

The main challenges shared by project partners were:

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- Involving more participants in the events. Partners will explore together with FRCT further communication strategies to increase the outreach of the future events. It is also recommended to organise joint events and to carefully plan the event according to its specific target.
- Collection of sex/gender-disaggregated data. Further efforts will be made to gather specific data and to promote the importance of the accessibility of this data.
- Not sufficient communication and dissemination of the GEP at institutional level. Further efforts will be made in order to raise awareness of GE and the GEP within each organisation's community.
- Low institutional involvement due to busy schedules. Project partners that are facing this challenge will study more efficient structures and planning of their GEPI Committees.
- Lack of interest in GE from some stakeholders. Project partners will examine new strategies to involve the community and effective ways of raising awareness.

Overall, it was also highlighted the importance of achieving sustainability of the GEPs and the involvement of the whole organisational staff from each RPO/RFO. Gabriela Langhammerová emphasised that it is key that highest management roles at the institutions get hold of the “ownership” of the GE topics and get directly involved in the implementation of the GEP.

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Annex – Agenda of the 2nd Mutual Learning Workshop

ATHENA H2020 project - Implementing GEPs to unlock research potential of RPOs and RFOs in Europe

AGENDA
📅 [January 17th 2023](#)
📍 [Virtual attendance: Link to connect **here**](#)
Meeting Time Zone: Brussels' time (CET)

Day 1
Date: Tuesday January 17th, 2023
Venue: [Jozef Stefan Institute](#)

2nd Mutual Learning Workshop (MLW)
Shared experiences in the process of implementing the GEP and the organisation of events and trainings

9.50h – 10.00h	Connect online
10.00h – 10.10h	Opening words from the ATHENA coordinator/JSI to be confirmed
10.10h – 10.25h	ATHENA progress Michelle Perello – ATHENA coordinator
10.25h – 12.30h	Shared experiences on the implementation of the ATHENA GEPs and the organisation of events and trainings JSI UJK UB ULPGC
15 minutes each	5 minutes break UVSK SAV URAK ACIISI - GOBCAN FRCT
12.30h – 13.00h	Coffee Break
13.00h – 13.50h	Workshop: Good practices in the implementation of GEPs Facilitator: Gabriela Langhammerová - Gender Equality Plans and Community for Change at the Centre for Gender and Science (NKC)
13.50h – 14.00h	Conclusions and event closure

www.athenaequality.eu

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101006416